

Proceedings

International Stable Fly Workshop

San José Costa Rica
April 16–20 2018

International Stable Fly Workshop Executive Summary

Stable fly (*Stomoxys calcitrans*) is an economically damaging pest impacting livestock production throughout much of the world. Environmentally sustainable and cost-effective tools for the management of this pest are needed. Several control technologies are currently in use; however, consistent control has not been achieved. An international workshop was held in Costa Rica 16-20 April 2018 to address issues created by outbreaks of this cosmopolitan pest. Stable flies have been observed developing in substrates composed of fresh decomposing residues of several crop plants including pineapple, coffee pulp, citrus foliage, fruits, vegetables, oil palm, sugar cane, banana rachis and rice straw. Internationally, stable flies are an increasingly important, emerging, pest with social and economic importance for dairy and beef farmers including public and political concerns in affected communities. They are among the most important arthropod pests of livestock in Brazil, Costa Rica, and USA. Although the economic threshold for stable flies has been established at 15-20 flies per animal, outbreaks of over 1000 stable flies per animal were observed in 2016 and 2017 in Costa Rica. Such infestation levels can reduce livestock productivity to near zero and cause mortality. Workshop attendees shared lessons learned in Costa Rica, USA, Europe, Africa and Brazil and developed plans for research on methodologies and technologies needed for the management of this plague.

Current stable fly control methods are expensive, time consuming, and not sustainable. Although the current research program being conducted by INTA (Costa Rica National Research Agriculture Institute) has been very productive, it lacks resources and expertise needed to address this very complex problem. In response to this situation, the workshop concluded that:

- 1) A Stable Fly Management Plan should be developed. The plan should contain specific recommended practices for mitigating the development of stable flies in agronomic and livestock associated residues and specific sampling methods and limits for compliance. Mechanisms for amending the plan should be included such that it remains relevant as new technologies for managing this pest are developed.
- 2) An extension program be established to train crop and livestock producers as well as the public on the biology, identification, and management of flies affecting livestock production in Costa Rica.
- 3) A comprehensive research program be developed on topics including developmental biology, adult dispersion and feeding behavior, toxicology and insecticide resistance, biological control, traps and targets, repellents and attractants, host-parasite interactions, animal welfare- production impacts, and economic thresholds.
- 4) Training be provided for INTA and other Costa Rican government scientist on veterinary entomology, toxicology, and molecular biology to improve the “in-house” ability to address the challenges posed by stable flies.
- 5) Training be provided for Costa Rican students in Veterinary Entomology, toxicology and molecular biology to support the next generation.
- 6) An advisory board consisting of a director from the ministry of livestock and agriculture and INTA and stakeholders representing crop and livestock producers and affected communities be formed to oversee the administration of regulatory, research and extension programs

The workshop participants thank Minister Luis Felipe Arauz Cavallini, Vice-Minister Ivannia Quesada, staffs of MAG, INTA and SENASA, and the livestock, coffee and pineapple producers for their hospitality and support during our visit.

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Monday, 16 April

The workshop began Monday morning with a meeting hosted by Minister Luis Felipe Arauz Cavallini (Costa Rica, MAG) and Vice-Minister Ivannia Quesada (Costa Rica, MAG). Attendees included Carlos Araya (Costa Rica, Executive Director, INTA), Anita Katial (US, FAS Regional Agricultural Counselor – Costa Rica, Nicaragua and Panama), Uli Bernier (US, ARS National Program Leader), representatives of the cattle, pineapple, coffee and oil palm industries in Costa Rica, MAG representatives and workshop participants. Minister Arauz, Vice-Minister Quesada and Executive Director Araya welcomed the workshop participants and gave overviews of the stable fly situation in Costa Rica, the importance of the pineapple industry to the country and the impacts of stable flies on cattle industries.

Following the opening session, the group traveled to CoopeTarrazú near San Marcos of Tarrazú to look at stable flies developing in coffee residues. Stable flies can develop in two byproducts of coffee processing, the composting coffee hulls and in thatch of fields where washing water, a mixture of water and coffee berry pulp, also referred to as honey water, is sprayed for disposal. Stable fly monitoring with Vavoua traps near the coffee residue composting areas was observed. The group returned to San Jose in the evening.

Tuesday, 17 April

Departed hotels about 7:30 AM for San Carlos. Visited Fyffes' Anexco pineapple farm. Mr. Rolando Pacheco described the process for growing pineapples and the procedures used to manage stable flies. Mr. Pacheco indicated that stable fly management cost pineapple producers US\$3,500-5,000 / hectare. Assuming $\frac{1}{2}$ of the 40,000+ hectares of pineapple production in Costa Rica is being renovated each year, stable fly management is costing the pineapple industry more than 75 million US dollars per year. During our visit, Anexco was using large excavators to bury pineapple residues in trenches with an overburden of ≈ 1 meter.

We proceeded to the stakeholders meeting at Marina San Carlos. Met with ≈ 100 stakeholders (Livestock and pineapple farmers). Presentations on stable fly impacts on the pineapple and livestock sectors, research and regulatory issues and international situation were made by representatives of the pineapple producers, Dos Pinos Dairy, Arturo Solórzano and David Taylor respectively. Following a lively question and answer session, the workshop participants proceeded to the Hotel Termal del Bosque.

Wednesday, 18 April

Departed hotel ≈7:30 AM and visited Tierra Fertil pineapple farm to observe stable fly development in chopped pineapple residues of various ages of fresh chopped and desiccated chopped pineapple and IGR insecticide trials. Workshop participants proceeded to Inprotsa pineapple farm to observe chopping process and sample fresh chopped residues for volatiles. Parasitoid releases, *Spalangia endius*, and trapping trials were observed. A sample of stable flies was collected for testing Permethrin susceptibility. Virtually no mortality was observed after 3-hour exposure to LD₉₉ dose of Permethrin. Vice-minister Quesada joined the group in the afternoon. Visited a small farm to observe effects of stable flies on cattle. Proceeded to Centro Internacional Genético Agrícola, toured *in vitro* fertilization laboratory and cattle paddocks. After a bit of R&R, participants went to the Exposición Pecuaria del Istmo Centroamericano (EXPICA) in San Carlos for the evening.

Thursday, 19 April

The symposium portion of the workshop began with a series of five talks presenting an overview of the stable fly situation internationally.

Costa Rica, Arturo Solórzano. Stable fly outbreaks associated with pineapple production were first reported in Costa Rica in 1987. Subsequently, outbreaks associated with citrus, rice straw, oil palm, coffee, and bananas have been reported. Investigations continue on sugarcane and vegetable crops to see if they are contributing to the stable fly outbreaks. INTA has been working to educate producers on the biology and identification of stable flies, especially how to differentiate stable flies from *Euxesta* spp. (Diptera: Ulidiidae) whose larvae are superficially similar to those of stable fly. Larval control measures include desiccating, chopping, and tilling residues along with

treatment with an IGR. Novaluron is the most frequently used IGR. In 2017 evidence of control failures were observed. Cyromazine and fipronil continue to provide good control. Adult stable flies are being controlled with white sticky traps and Vavoua traps routinely. Thermal fogging with 2.5% deltamethrin is being used in emergency situations. Biological control trials using *Spalangia endius* are showing good results with up to 70% parasitism under good conditions. Coordination among researchers, Ministry of Ag, INTA, SENASA, Plant Health, municipalities, farmers, and the public is key to solving this problem.

Brazil, Thadeu Barros. Over the last decade, population explosions of the stable fly have become an unprecedented problem affecting several Brazilian states. Yearly outbreaks are closely related to sugarcane processing and compromise livestock production in surrounding areas with economic, social and environmental implications. Stable fly outbreaks in Brazil are mostly associated with organic residues/by-products from ethanol production in sugarcane mills. The first outbreak occurred in 1973. In 1978, dumping vinasse in bodies of water was banned. In 1998, a graduated ban on burning sugarcane was implemented. No outbreaks were recorded until 2008 when outbreaks were reported in three municipalities. By 2016, outbreaks were reported in 105 municipalities from five states. A stable fly working group was formed in Sao Paulo state in 2015, controlled burning of sugarcane residues was permitted in 2016 and a stable fly management program was implemented in 2017. Regulatory issues are being discussed in other states to reduce the problem and its consequences.

Australia, David Taylor (for David Cook). Stable flies have been around for over 300 years BUT in the last 20 years have become an “emerging pest.” Stable fly outbreaks are observed most frequently in the Swan River Coastal Plain surrounding Perth, Western Australia. The area is characterized by having a coarse sandy soil and is ideal for vegetable crop production. Initially, stable fly larvae were observed in vegetable plots fertilized with untreated poultry manure which led to a ban on transporting or applying poultry manure within the control zone. Subsequently, stable fly larvae have been observed in residues of more than 30 vegetable crops including broccoli, celery, cabbage, and cauliflower. Management options include ceasing irrigation, tilling the crop under, and compressing the overburden with rollers. In 2007 Australia passed the Biosecurity and Agriculture Management Act and in 2013 the Stable Fly Management Plan was implemented and then amended in 2016 (SFMP, Appendix II). The SFMP includes mandated procedures for managing manures, crop residues, and livestock. In addition to the SFMP, the Western Australia Department of Primary Industries and Regional Development produced a Training Manual for stable fly inspectors (Appendix III). The manual contains sampling procedures and compliance thresholds as well as information on development and identification of stable flies.

Africa, Asia and France, Gerard Duvallet. Although those working on stable flies in the Western Hemisphere deal with a single species, *Stomoxys calcitrans*, there are 51 species of Stomoxyini in the World. Twelve species of *Stomoxys* are endemic to Africa, four are endemic in Asia, and one (*S. sitiens*) is found in both Africa and Asia. Only *S. calcitrans* is cosmopolitan. In Africa, one species (*S. xanthomelas*) lives in the canopy feeding on monkeys and maybe a vector of emerging diseases being transmitted to humans. Most of the traps currently used for stable fly control were originally developed for tsetse flies (*Glossina* spp.). Recent studies indicate stable flies are most sensitive to reflected light at 460 nm. New plastic screen reflects about 80% of light whereas cloth reflects only 40%. Blue and white plastic panels impregnated with insecticides are patent pending. Management program on La Reunion Island used vavoua traps, repellents, spraying insecticides, spray cattle with water when milking, parasitoids, to control stable flies. Program was terminated and incidence of Bovine Leucosis has been increasing. Management program being reinstated. Genetic studies indicate *S. indicus* (a species endemic to Asia) is basal to all other *Stomoxys* spp. This indicates that the group may have arisen in southern Asia rather than Africa as currently believed. In France as well as much of the rest of Europe, incidence of Besnoitiosis is increasing.

Populations of stable flies from around the Veterinary School in Toulouse have high levels of resistance to pyrethroids (but still susceptible to phoxim). Economic thresholds for stable flies will vary from country to country depending upon livestock breeds and values, labor costs, and chemical insecticide costs among other things.

United States, David Taylor. As in Europe, stable flies in the United States are usually associated with developing in livestock wastes. However, this has not always been the case. In 1913, Bishopp indicated that the primary source of stable flies were straw piles. As a result of modern cultural practices, straw piles are no longer left in fields after grain processing and are therefore no longer a source for stable fly development. The primary recommendation for stable fly management in the United States involve sanitation in livestock production facilities. Recent data based upon morphometrics of flies developing in livestock wastes and flies caught on sticky traps as adults indicate that a significant proportion may not be developing in livestock wastes. Is it possible that stable flies are developing in other substrates at lower levels? Yield loss models indicate that stable flies are costing livestock producers in the US more than \$2 billion per year in lost revenues (unpublished estimates using the same model updated to 2016 indicate the cost has increased to over \$3 billion). There are no specific regulations for managing stable flies in the US nor does there appear to be public demand for such regulations. Education is an important component of this lack of interest. Most producers cannot differentiate between species of muscoid flies infesting their livestock and hence do not see stable flies as a specific problem.

Biology of stable flies, immatures and adults, Gerard Duvallet. Most Stomoxines have limited ecological niche relative to *S. calcitrans* which is usually limited to human modified habitats. Four taxa, *S. bengalensis*, *S. indicus*, *S. sitiens*, and *S. niger niger* are primarily associated with human influenced habitats. Other species such as *S. inornatus*, *S. omega*, *S. pallidus*, *S. transvittatus*, and *S. xanthomelas* are found only in primary forest habitats. Two species, *S. calcitrans* and *S. niger niger* are found on La Reunion Island. Although development time of pre-imaginal stages relative to temperature are similar, *S. calcitrans* populations have higher rate of increase at lower temperatures whereas *S. niger niger* populations have higher rate of increase at higher temperatures. Temperature (=elevation) and moisture have the greatest impact on larval development and survival. No indication of reproductively isolated populations of either species on La Reunion Island. Stable fly mating pheromones are contact pheromones with low volatility. Stable flies directly cause anxiety and stress, blood spoliation, decreased immune response, weight loss, and milk production loss in cattle. Indirectly, they are vectors viruses (Equine Infectious Anemia & Bovine Leukemia), bacteria (*Bacillus anthracis* & *Anaplasma marginale*) and protozoa (*Trypanosoma* spp. & *Besnoitia* spp.). Most of these pathogens are limited to the Eastern Hemisphere. Used FitBit attached to tail of equines and bovines to evaluate efficacy of repellents. The mechanism of attraction of alsynite sticky traps (and white traps) is not known. When the traps are located distant from potential hosts, their catch appears to be biased towards males (1:2 ratio ♀:♂). Although adult stable flies have been observed to disperse long distances (>200 km), pest level dispersion of a population from larval developmental sites appears to be limited to 1.5-2.0 km when hosts are available. **It is likely stable flies will disperse as far as necessary to locate hosts and oviposition sites.**

Substrate properties and microbial communities, David Taylor. Stable fly larvae can develop in a wide variety of decomposing vegetative materials, often mixed with animal feces or urine. David Cook has recorded over 50 distinct substrates suitable for larval development (Appendix IV). The primary question is – What defines a suitable substrate for stable fly larval development? Our hypothesis is that stable fly larvae are dependent upon the microbial community of the substrate either directly or indirectly for nutrients and that the microbial community is dependent upon the physical and chemical properties of the substrate. Depth, moisture and temperature are the most important physical properties of the substrate. The probability of finding stable fly larvae

in a substrate sample increase with depth from 0-30 cm. Depth most likely acts as a buffer, moderating changes in temperature and moisture with changing environmental conditions. For moisture, the probability of finding larvae was highest at $\approx 350\%$ water ($\approx 3.5\text{g H}_2\text{O/g}$ dry material) and for temperature, between 25 and 30° C. The optimal air temperature for maximum stable fly populations was $\approx 20^\circ$ C. Electrical conductivity is correlated with pH, inorganic Nitrogen and the probability of larvae being present. Optimal pH for stable fly larvae is between 7.0 and 8.5. Microbial communities were biased towards *Dysgonomonas* and *Proteiniphilum* in substrate samples with stable fly larvae. Larval behavioral assays indicate that stable fly larvae are highly attracted to ammonium and favored substrates high in inorganic nitrogen.

Host Interactions, Eliud Herrera. The bites and feeding of stable flies directly reduce productivity of the animals. They stop feeding, wade into the rivers, vegetation, etc. for protection. Economic thresholds for stable flies have not been established in Costa Rica. Losses include loss of milk, meat and abortions. Actual, country data, are lacking. This is a serious knowledge gap. Effects of climate and low feed quality on animals in conjunction with stable fly infestations are unknown. Producers believe flies are the only problem, however lost productivity is a combination of flies, climate, humidity, food, and foot issues – i.e. general animal husbandry. Cattle reproduction is a key measure and can be significantly reduced in a year following an outbreak. It is important to correlate all factors – not just the number of flies. Livestock defensive behaviors can be used to assess fly numbers, tail movement, bunching etc. Currently, there is no program to maintain surveillance for livestock diseases in Costa Rica. It is difficult to relate the number of larvae in a sample of developmental substrate to infestation levels of livestock. There are too many variables such as area of substrate, number of animals at risk, status of neighboring croplands, weather etc. A general guideline used by some is that less than 8 immatures in a sample area ($\approx 10 \times 10$ cm) is acceptable but more than 10 immatures is likely to result in troublesome adult populations. Management methods that can reliably reduce immature populations to these levels are needed. Cattle producers in Costa Rica are reluctant to commit resources to manage stable flies because they feel that it is completely the responsibility of pineapple producers. Research on the development and impacts of stable flies on livestock under tropical (Costa Rica) conditions is needed.

Genomics, Pia Olafson. Efforts to sequence the genome of *Stomoxys calcitrans* were funded by an NIH grant to Serap Aksoy (Yale University). Stable fly was sequenced as a haematophagous outgroup for a larger study of tsetse fly (*Glossina* spp.) genomes. A strain for sequencing was developed by 11 generations of sibling mating to reduce heterozygosity. Eight functional gene systems were analyzed in depth, chemosensory, visual, reproduction and development, immune pathways, salivary proteins, sex determination, transcription factors, and detoxification pathways. The stable fly genome is being maintained in VectorBase. Options for using genomics to study population structure and insecticide resistance in stable flies and microbial communities in substrates were discussed. Potential applications for genomics in stable fly management efforts include:

- Use Odor Binding Proteins to create better repellents
- Population genetics of stable flies using genotyping by sequencing
- Characterizing the microbial communities of developmental substrates
- Characterization of metabolic enzymes such as P450s, Esterases, & ABC transporters used to detoxify environmental chemicals and insecticides

Cultural control, Ronald González. Most of the pineapple production is located in the northern Atlantic regions of Costa Rica. Pineapple has a production cycle of approximately two years. The first pineapple is produced approximately 13 months after planting. The second about 11 months later. Following harvest of the second crop, fields are renovated. Plants may be desiccated with Paraquat before chopping. Plants are usually treated with an IGR, chopped and then tilled into the soil. Multiple passes for chopping and tilling are needed to completely incorporate plant residues. Approximately 200 metric tons of plant residue per hectare. Female stable flies are attracted to the plant residues and oviposit immediately after shredding. Burning the fields reduces stable fly development, but has environmental consequences and reduces soil fertility. Bacterial decomposers accelerate the decomposition process, but they do not significantly reduce stable fly development. Pineapple plant cores resist the chopping and tilling process offering suitable substrate for stable fly larval development. Rainfall can retard the tilling process and is conducive for larval development. Fields are monitored for stable flies starting 5 days after “knockdown” and then every 5 days. Samples are taken from six locations per hectare. Sampling is directed towards areas with high biomass and moisture. Correct identification of fly larvae is important. *Euxesta* spp. larvae can coexist with *Stomoxys* larvae and are superficially similar. White sticky traps, 15 traps / hectare are used to monitor fields for stable fly activity as well as Vavoua and emergence traps. Following tilling and decomposition of the plant residues, planting beds and drainage structures are reconstructed and “seed” plants are planted. Stable fly management is dependent upon integrated cultural control practices, proper crop residue management (rainfall is a primary limiting factor), careful and timely monitoring of immature stages. Research is needed to find an oviposition repellent that prevents the flies from laying their eggs in the pineapple residues and on better and faster ways to dry the residues to render them unsuitable for stable fly development. Possibly most important, research is needed on the effects on soil condition and fertility of removing the residues. With current technologies, even if everything is done correctly, heavy rains can undo the management efforts and outbreaks are inevitable.

Chemical Ecology.

Jerry Zhu. Stable flies use olfactory cues for host and oviposition site location. Semiochemicals can be used for “push-pull” control strategies. Repellents are used to push flies away from livestock or larval developmental substrates and repellents combined with toxicants or traps are used to pull flies away from livestock and eliminate them from the population. Catnip oil (15% formulation) very effective repellent, but has only 5-hour residual activity. A new, patent pending, compound has greater than two-week residual activity in laboratory assays. A 6.6% formulation of this compound had 4 days of residual activity in field tests and costs \$13 for 4,000 liters of formulation. Toxicity is low as this compound is currently used in edible products. Manure slurry is highly attractive to stable flies. Key volatiles are methoxy-phenyl oxime, phenol, m-cresol, p-cresol, and 4 ethylphenol. Vinasse, a byproduct of ethanol production from sugar cane, is highly attractive for stable flies. Stable fly eyes are most sensitive to light in the ranges of 420-440nm (blue), 530-540 nm (green), and 610-630 nm (red). White traps which reflect all three of these colors were most effective for collecting adult stable flies. Although pattern may be important, plain white traps still appear to be best. Research is needed on the effects of light reflectance and polarization on stable fly attractancy of trap surfaces.

Francisco Gonzalez. Director of Research and Development for Chemtica. Chemtica is currently selling Vavoua traps for Vestergaard S.A. in Costa Rica and providing *Spalangia endius* under an agreement with INTA. Insects have two main interests, food and sex. Adults stable flies require food in the form of hosts and females require substrates in which to lay their eggs. Both involve volatile cues are therefore useful. Sex pheromones in most muscoid Diptera are contact in nature and therefore non-volatile and of little use for management. Among other compounds found in

dung, 1-octen-3-ol, acetophenone, phenol, and p -cresol are important. For effective control of stable flies, two attractants will probably be needed, one for recently emerged and host seeking flies and the other for females searching for oviposition sites. Also, attractant compounds need to be evaluated in combinations. Ratios and doses will be important.

Traps and Monitoring, Jerry Hogsette and Georgina Bingham. Trapping is complex and flies can't read! Understanding behavior is important when designing traps. Stable flies need structure, i.e. a place to land and rest. Alsynite traps were developed by Williams in the 1970s-1980s. Attraction is essentially visual with an adhesive painted on the trap. Experience has shown the producers do not want to make traps or targets, they prefer to buy them. The glue used for sticky traps is an important component of the trapping system. Not all glues are equally effective. Stable flies tend to circle around traps and targets before entering or landing. Therefore, sticky traps can be placed next to targets to evaluate effectiveness. Blue/black cloth traps and targets were originally designed for tsetse fly control. In the long term, traps such as the Vavoua trap are less expensive and more environmentally friendly than single use plastic white sticky traps. Warning labels on traps will be tested to help reduce theft. The combination of blue and black does not appear to be required for attracting stable flies in the USA. In comparisons, pure black attracted the most, pure blue next, and blue/black least number of flies. Nzi traps collect large numbers of flies, but they are cumbersome and many of the flies do not enter the trap. Long lasting insecticide treated fences/screens surrounding cattle reduce the number of flies biting the animals. Research is needed on the relationship between physiological status of the flies and their level of attraction to different trap designs.

Biological Control,

Chris Geden. Stable flies have many natural enemies, but only a few are commercially available. Fungal pathogens (*Beauveria* & *Metarhizium*) take over 8 days to kill stable fly adults and ineffective against larvae. Parasitic wasps (*Muscidifurax*, *Spalangia*) lay eggs on fly pupa. One wasp can kill 35-200 pupae in her lifetime. *Muscidifurax* spp. have a shorter development time, shorter adult life, higher attack rate, forage near surface of habitat, prefer dryer substrates, are very sensitive to pesticides, and many pupae are killed by wasp feeding rather than parasitization. *Spalangia* spp. on the other hand have a longer development time, longer adult life, lower attack rate, forage deeper in substrates for buried host pupae, are more effective in wet conditions, and are more tolerant of some pesticides. Quality control and proper implementation are important to the success of parasitic wasps for controlling flies. *Spalangia endius* is a good "all purpose" parasitoid that is effective outdoors and can locate deeply buried fly pupae. Research is critically needed to determine appropriate release rates and methods for fly suppression in pineapple, coffee, and sugarcane crop residues.

Jairo Trevino Pinedo Del Monte. *Spalangia endius* is a good candidate for fly control in subtropical and tropical climates and they are effective at finding fly pupae buried in substrates. Experiments were conducted to evaluate insecticide resistance and foraging depth for *S. endius*. *S. endius* were very sensitive to Etoprop (an organophosphate insecticide) but resistant to Rimon 10E (novaluron, IGR). *S. endius* effectively parasitized stable fly pupae buried up to 15 cm below the surface in substrate. In a field trial, *S. endius* adults were released when the first stable fly pupae were observed (11-12 days after shredding) and emergence traps were used to evaluate the number of viable stable flies emerging from the substrate. *S. endius* reduced the number of stable flies emerging and number of viable pupae in the test plots by about 50% relative to untreated plots. Care must be taken to properly time the parasitoid releases. Additional research is needed to determine the best parasitoid species for release and the best methods for releasing / distributing the parasitoids.

Avelino José Bittencourt UFRRJ. *Metarhizium* and *Beauveria* did not work well, but *Lecanicillium* (*Verticillium*) did. The action of the fungi is not immediate, but rather extended throughout the life cycle of the fly. Biological control agents can complement insecticides and other chemical control methods. Antifungal compounds produced by a bacterium that was part of stable fly larval microbiota, *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia*, rendered them resistant to *Beauveria*. The entomopathogenic nematode *Heterorhabditis bacteriophora* provided > 90% control of stable fly larvae in laboratory assays. The goal is to introduce infective juvenile nematodes into the vinasse before use in fertigation. Water pressure in the fertigation systems should not affect the viability of the infective juvenile nematodes. The nematodes can be mass reared relatively inexpensively. The nematodes only infect arthropods. Field efficacy studies of the nematodes are needed.

Chemical Control and Resistance, Arturo Solórzano and Troy Anderson. Up to 2010, all available insecticides were being applied to pineapple residues. In 2011, diflubenzuron emerged as the most frequently used. INTA began work at that time on different insect growth regulators. Differences in effectiveness were observed. In 2012-2013, insecticides were applied weekly. Biological pesticides were tested in 2017, but with limited success. Some tests in 2017 resulted in lower than expected control with diflubenzuron. In a second test in 2018, diflubenzuron worked as expected. Diflubenzuron is mobile in water. High precipitation may have washed the insecticide away thus reducing efficacy. Screening assays to identify diflubenzuron resistance need to be developed and field populations screened. Larvicides with alternate modes of action such as Cyromazine should be used in rotation with the benzoylureas to retard the development of resistance in the stable flies. Tests on decomposers in 2013 showed that they did not effectively reduce the number of stable flies developing in the pineapple residues. The products took about a week before showing activity and by then the stable flies were developed enough that they could survive. Thermofogging with 2% Deltamethrin has been used in pastures to protect cattle since 2016. During our visit, flies collected from traps at the Inprotsa Pineapple Farm were tested with the LD₉₉ dose of Permethrin. No mortality was observed. Screening those flies for the *kdr-His* mutation which can confer higher tolerance to permethrin revealed that the mutant allele was present at a frequency of 0.75. This indicates a relatively high level of permethrin resistance in the population. Field populations of stable flies should be screened for permethrin and deltamethrin resistance.

Regulatory Issues, David Meneses. Stable flies have been a problem in Costa Rica for about 25 years, but in the last 5 years the government has been pushing for more regulations. Stable flies are a very adaptable pest, growing well even in very unfavorable conditions. All livestock and crop producers must monitor their facilities for stable flies. In 2012 regulations were enacted requiring farmers to act on the recommendations of MAG. According to Article 8 phytosanitary services cannot implement sanctions, however animal health (SENASA) can. In 2011, there was a re-organization to solve article 8 issues. The vice minister set up different groups including a whatsapp group. Regional teams get buy in from all groups and work together on stable fly issues using not only regulations, but also capacity building, workshops, and community awareness. Pineapple farms directly employ 1 employees per HA and indirectly 3 employees per HA. SENASA responsible for enforcement and issues sanitary orders. If farmers do not comply, sanctions are invoked. INTA is responsible for research and protocols. Pineapple is Costa Rica's largest export (> \$1 billion USD / year). Desiccation of the plants with herbicides (Paraquat) or burning of the residues are the most effective methods for managing stable flies in pineapple crop residues. However, these methods are restricted by several importing nations.

Recommendations

The research questions should be investigated in parallel through the following activities:

- ✓ Formation of International Stable Fly Working Group (initiated at workshop)
- ✓ Laboratory & field experiments (initial experiments planned at workshop)
- ✓ Interchange of students & scientists from involved countries
- ✓ Testing of commercial & non-commercial products
- ✓ Scientific meetings & workshops (next meeting planned for October 2019 in Brazil)
- ✓ Education & tech transfer meetings, providing locally relevant advice & recommendations
- ✓ Publication of scientific, extension & popular press materials

Research Needs

1. Larval biology
2. Adult biology
3. Parasitoids and natural enemies
4. Chemical Ecology
5. Trapping methods
6. Economic threshold for trapping and larval development in plant residues
7. Cattle behavior/defensive movements
8. Further Monitoring: Potential new techniques
9. Chemical control
10. Training and education
11. Extension services, including audits related to imposed sanctions, and technology transfer

Research Needs Expanded and Collaborations:

Biology:

1. Larval biology: INTA & USDA

- a. What makes a stable fly habitat / developmental substrate?
 - i. Substrates
 - Identify current and novel substrates
 - Effects of substrate “quality” on developmental rates; size and life history parameters, reproduction, biting;
 - ii. Are larvae feeding on the microbial community and is this the defining characteristic of the larval substrate – could antimicrobials be used as control agents
 - Microbial interactions

2. Adult biology: INTA, USDA, & VOLARE

- a. Dispersal; distances, direction & environmental interactions
- b. Feeding; preferences, number of times (impacts economic thresholds), and length of time feeding, how much blood are the animals losing, partial feedings. This data will dictate how often & how long you should make you counts
- c. Phenology; interactions between environmental parameters, precipitation, temperature, to create predictions of outbreaks based on weather – in order to schedule agronomic & control practices

Monitoring & Control Measures:

3. Parasitoids and natural enemies: USDA, INTA, & IAEA

- a. Survey natural communities
- b. Define which species have greatest potential
- c. Management techniques with parasitoids
 - i. Dispersal, dispensing, release rates (Solórzano & González in progress)
 - ii. Monitoring efficacy ((Solórzano & González in progress)

- iii. Rearing within Medfly colonies – in order to mass rear within IAEA facilities
- 4. Chemical ecology (attractants & repellents):** INTA, USDA, Chentica & EMBRAPA
 - a. Identify vegetation associated attractants, oviposition cues (Solórzano, Gonzalez & Zhu, in progress)
 - b. Identify host associated attractants and repellents
 - c. Identify novel repellents (Zhu, in progress)
 - d. Dispensing
 - e. Field use, efficacy
 - 5. Trapping:** INTA, IAEA, USDA, Vestergaard, EMBRAPA & VOLARE
 - a. Optimizing trap design, including use of attractants (Solorzano, Gonzalez & Zhu, in progress)
 - b. Evaluate effects of long lasting insecticide treatment of traps
 - c. Possible age and sex biases of traps
 - d. Trap positioning (Duvallet & Hogsette, in progress)
 - e. Timing
 - f. Number of traps required per hectare (Duvallet & Hogsette, in progress)
 - 6. Action threshold for trapping and larval development in plant residues:** INTA, USDA & EMBRAPA
 - a. Relate trap numbers and larval densities to adult numbers and economic thresholds
 - i. How many larvae/m² means a level low, medium, high
 - ii. How many adults/trap/week are OK
E.g. what does 30 flies per trap per day mean; are we reaching/ exceeding our goals
 - 7. Cattle behavior/defensive movements:** INTA & IAEA
 - a. Relationship to infestation levels
 - b. Impact of stable flies
 - i. Physiological damage or behavioral or both
 - ii. Acclimation of cattle to stable fly infestations
 - 8. Further Monitoring:**

Potential new techniques - Drones for interpretation of sites according with the spectro IR and the relation with climate variables like RH and rain; to help to identify possible risk sites for future development of SF a tool for the plant health inspectors.
 - 9. Chemical control and resistance:** INTA USDA, EMBRAPA & VOLARE
 - a. New insecticides for replacement / rotation with IGR group (Solórzano in progress)
 - b. Assessment of resistance to IGRs and Pyrethroids (Olafson & Castro, in progress)
 - 10. Training needs:**
 - a. Experimental design and statistical analyses
 - b. Cattle insect identification
 - c. Cattle defensive movement assessment - attach the procedure from SENASA
 - d. Pest prediction model
 - e. PCR analysis of Stable flies

- 11. Extension services, including audits related to sanctions and technology transfer:** SENASA, SFE, MAG, USDA, INTA, independent and associated (ICAFE; CANAPEP; Conarroz, livestock (dairy and meat), citrus & oil palm):
- a. Develop workshops and research seminars for stakeholders, researchers and administrators
 - b. Develop procedures and standards for producers and regulators
 - c. Sponsor field days and pilot studies to demonstrate effective waste management procedures
 - d. Develop brochures, digital and print, to transfer technology to producers

Appendix I – Participants and Biographies

Appendix II – Stable fly management plan

Appendix III – Stable fly Inspector Training Manual

Appendix IV – Larval developmental substrates

Appendix IV – Stable Fly Pineapple plant residues example management plan.

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Thadeu Barros, PhD, veterinary entomologist of the Brazilian Agricultural Research Corporation (Embrapa) since 1987, currently at Embrapa Beef Cattle. Former member of the FAO Working Group on Parasite Resistance and FAO/Industry Contact Group on Parasite Resistance (2003-2009); currently a member of the Technical Committee on Animal Parasitosis and Resistance to Antiparasitics of the Brazilian Ministry of Agriculture, Livestock and Food Supply (2016, current). Major area of interest: veterinary entomology, with emphasis on biology, ecology, chemical/biological control, and resistance to insecticides in livestock pests.

Georgina Bingham, PhD, serves as the technical expert and portfolio manager of the Food Security business at Vestergaard, a global company dedicated to improving the health of vulnerable people, especially those living in developing countries. Within this role she has collaborated with the USDA and the Costa Rican Ministry of Agriculture to combat the impact stable flies.

Georgina has more than 13 years' experience in vector, biting fly and stored product pest control in developing regions including sub-Saharan Africa Southeast Asia, Central & South America, and holds qualifications for project management and good clinical practice. She is also a Fellow of the Royal Entomological Society. Georgina has a strong research and development background in agriculture and biochemistry; with a BSc (hons) in Agricultural/Animal Science from Edinburgh University; completed MSc courses (Erasmus) in Animal Physiology & Production at Wageningen University and a PhD focused on xenobiotic resistance mechanisms from Imperial College London – based at Rothamsted Research UK & the Department of Primary Industries NSW Australia. She held post-doctoral posts funded through competitive grant proposals collaborating on projects with various global research institutions and private industry. Currently within her role at Vestergaard, she is an adjunct Associate Professor within the Entomology Department at the University of Nebraska, Lincoln.

Avelino José Bittencourt, PhD, Veterinarian, MsC, PhD in Veterinary Parasitology at the Federal Rural University of Rio de Janeiro. Senior Professor of Semiology at the same university since 1998. Works with *Stomoxys calcitrans* since 1994. Worked with seasonality, epidemiology, evaluation of cutaneous lesions, animal behavioral alterations, biological control (fungi and nematodes) and applied biology to the residues of the sugar cane industry.

Gérard Duvallet, PhD, born in 1948, medical and veterinary entomologist, professor emeritus at Paul-Valéry University, Montpellier, France, and member of the Center for functional and evolutive ecology (CEFE: <https://www.cefe.cnrs.fr/en/research/biodiversity-and-conservation/anthropised-systems-ecology/1061-french/recherche/bc/eaaa/ec/178-gerard-duvallet>). Former President of the French Society for Parasitology. Has spent 21 years in Africa, working on human and animal trypanosomoses. After his return to France in 1994, he started to work on biting flies, mainly Stomoxyinae and Tabanidae. Systematics, phylogeny, phylogeography, population dynamics and control methods were the main subjects. Field activities are performed in France and in Thailand. More than 100 publications in peer-reviewed journals: (https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Gerard_Duvallet/contributions)

Partner of a French research project entitled FlyScreen (2015-2019), associating France, Thailand, Tanzania and Burkina Faso, for the development of new targets to control stable and horse flies.

Taciany Ferreira, PhD, Graduation in Biological Sciences at Uniderp University (2009). Master in Environment and Regional Development (2011) by the same University. Experience with Agricultural Entomology with emphasis on Phytosanitary, working on Integrated Pest Management. Acted as Distance Teacher-Tutor-Technology Course in Public Management - Distance Education Center - University Anhanguera Uniderp. PhD for the Postgraduate Course in Animal Science, Federal University of Mato Grosso do Sul (UFMS), in partnership with

Embrapa Gado de Corte, with emphasis on the monitoring of population dynamics and alternatives for control of *Stomoxys calcitrans* in the vicinity of sugarcane plants. She is currently responsible for the company Volare Consultoria Ambiental Ltda., through the provision of services for the population monitoring of stable flies and prevention and control of outbreaks in sugarcane and livestock farms. In addition, she promotes lectures, training and technical training for events involving public and private companies.

Christopher Geden, PhD, is a Research Entomologist with USDA-ARS Center for Medical, Agricultural and Veterinary Entomology, and has over 40 years of experience working on the biology and management of flies. Dr. Geden received his BS in Biology from Boston College (1976) and his MS and PhD in Entomology from the University of Massachusetts Amherst in 1979 and 1983. After working as a postdoc at North Carolina State University and a Research Associate at Cornell University, he took his current position with the USDA-ARS lab in Gainesville, FL, in 1992. His primary research focus has been on behavior and biological control of flies, especially house fly. Since receiving his Ph.D. in Entomology, he has authored over 114 papers in refereed scientific journals, written 4 book chapters, co-edited a book, and authored 45 popular and extension articles. Dr. Geden has also received patents for two pest control inventions. He has given over 25 international presentations, organized several symposia at national scientific meetings and been a co-organizer of two national conferences. In 2015 he received the Lifetime Achievement Award in Veterinary Entomology from the Livestock Insects Workers Conference. He is a subject editor for the Journal of Medical Entomology and serves on the Governing Board of the Entomological Society of America. <https://www.ars.usda.gov/southeast-area/gainesville-fl/center-for-medical-agricultural-and-veterinary-entomology/mosquito-and-fly-research/people/christopher-geden/>

Francisco Gonzalez, PhD: I was trained as biotechnologist in Costa Rica, Master in Plant Sciences with specialization in Entomology in Wageningen and Research Centre, The Netherlands, and graduated as doctor in Biology in the Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Sweden. During the first years of my career I focused on the use of microbials and invertebrates for the biological control of agricultural pests linked to the company Koppert Biological Systems in Spain, The Netherlands and Central America. However, during the last 8 years I have changed gears and explored the chemical ecology aspects of entomology, focusing on attractants and repellents for insect control. As Director of Research and Development of the company ChemTica I propose, develop, advise and supervise projects all around the globe. Among those projects, I am in charge of assuring the production of parasitoids for the control of *Spalangia endius* in Costa Rica, and the development of attractants and repellents against the stable fly (*Stomoxys calcitrans*) along with USDA personnel.

Jerome A. Hogsette, PhD, is a Research Entomologist with the USDA at the CMAVE Laboratory in Gainesville, Florida, and has nearly 40 years of experience in the field of Veterinary Entomology. His Ph.D. Dissertation topic was the management of house flies on poultry farms with a focused use of pesticides, biological control, growth regulators, habitat modification and sanitation. Dr. Hogsette has since worked nationally and internationally on projects to manage stable flies and house flies around domestic and exotic animals, in urban and rural locations, with many types of techniques, including traps, attractants and repellents. Early work demonstrated a 225-km flight range for stable flies with weather systems and a local flight speed of 8 km per hour. Dr. Hogsette is the author or co-author of more than 200 refereed publications, review articles, book chapters and extension articles, with 3 patents and numerous publications in the popular press. Dr. Hogsette has mentored 25 graduate students. <https://www.ars.usda.gov/southeast->

area/gainesville-fl/center-for-medical-agricultural-and-veterinary-entomology/mosquito-and-fly-research/people/jerome-hogsette/

Pia Untalan Olafson, PhD is a molecular biologist with the USDA-ARS, Livestock Arthropod Pests Research Unit in Kerrville, TX. Her work primarily focuses on elucidating biochemical pathways that are critical to host-ectoparasite interactions, as they relate to stable flies, horn flies, and cattle fever ticks. Her research interests include biting fly chemosensation and pesticide resistance. She is a member of the multi-state project, “Fly Management in Animal Agriculture Systems and Impacts on Animal Health and Food Safety”, and she is the co-director of the Stable Fly Genome Sequencing Consortium, working collaboratively with government and university researchers to manually curate and publish the stable fly genome. (PhD, 2002, University of Hawai‘i – Mānoa).

José Arturo Solórzano Arroyo. Master Scientiae M.Sc. Colegio Posgraduados de México. Posgraduate Universidad de Costa Rica. Bachelor Universidad de Costa Rica. Entomologist at Instituto Nacional de Innovación y Transferencia en Tecnología Agropecuaria (INTA) of Costa Rica. Development of basic and applied research on the Stable Fly (*Stomoxys calcitrans*: Diptera Muscidae) reproduced in pineapple, oil palm, coffee pulp, and citrus trees plant residues. Assessment of impact of *S. calcitrans* affecting livestock in Costa Rica: Determination of morphological characteristics for identification of larvae, pupae and adults of the stable fly and differentiation of other Diptera associated with pineapple stubble. Evaluation of biological efficiency of biological decomposers used with shredder pineapple residues for pest control. Insecticides chemical control assessment of larvae and adults. Biology and behavior of *Stomoxys calcitrans* in pineapple crops and other plants crops. Dynamics population of stable fly during rainy and dry season. Stable fly trapping efficiency of sticky glue plastic and fabric blue-black, number and frequency of monitoring. Rearing *Stomoxys calcitrans* in laboratory at INTA’s Lab in Costa Rica, sampling SF at pineapple farms development of tools for larvae sampling. Rearing process of wasp *Spalangia endius* for parasitism of stable fly and field commercial use, assessment of control of biological control of released parasitoid. Fresh plant volatiles capture to determine attractants for Stable Fly field experiments with SPME capture on pineapple and coffee plant residues. Surveillance of outbreaks of Stable Fly in coffee, pineapple, citrus, banana and oil palm crops. Training of Stable Fly biology, diagnostic and integrate pest management to producer and official technicians of government of Costa Rica. Speaker at national and international seminars about research for Stable Fly control methods and behavior of the pest in Costa Rica.

David Taylor, PhD, is a Research Entomologist with USDA-ARS Agroecosystem Management Research Unit in Lincoln, Nebraska and has over 35 years of experience in Veterinary Entomology. Dr. Taylor received his BS and PhD degrees from the University of Notre Dame in 1977 and 1982 respectively. Dr. Taylor began his professional career with ARS in 1983 working on screwworm genetics and mass rearing technologies at the Screwworm Research Laboratory in Tuxtla Gutiérrez, Chiapas, Mexico. In 1991 Dr. Taylor moved to the USDA-ARS Midwest Livestock Insect Research Laboratory in Lincoln, Nebraska and in 1994 began a research program on flies affecting livestock production with an emphasis on stable flies which he continues today. He has worked on biological control, genetics, ecology and management of stable flies and other muscoid flies associated with livestock. During a 40+ year research career, he has published 62 journal articles and 4 book chapters. [https://works.bepress.com/david_taylor/].

Jerry (Junwei) Zhu, PhD, is a Research Chemical Ecologist/Entomologist at USDA-ARS. He is also an Adjunct Professor of Entomology at the University of Nebraska since 2010. He received his PhD in Chemical Ecology in 1995. He has worked in various universities, Industry and Research Institutes in US and Europe. His research focuses on semiochemical-based pest management (particularly in discovering novel natural repellent/attractant compounds and

practical applications). He has over 100 scientific publications, with 6 US patents and several developed commercial products from his inventions. Dr. Zhu has conducted chemical ecological studies on biting flies (including stable flies) in the last 10 years, and he has published many research papers on the discovery and development of using semiochemicals associated to fly habitats, livestock animals and plant-origin repellents for stable fly control. He has also served as a guest editor of *Journal of Chemical Ecology* for the special issue titled, "Semiochemicals in Pest Management: Development, Regulation Applications". He is a subject Editor of ESA journal "Journal of Insect Science" and joined editorial boards of several international journals. He is the President-Elected of ISCE (2018). He previously served as the Presidents of Asia-Pacific Association of Chemical Ecologists and the Overseas Chinese Entomologists of America.

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BIOSECURITY AND AGRICULTURE MANAGEMENT ACT 2007

**BIOSECURITY AND
AGRICULTURE MANAGEMENT
(STABLE FLY)
MANAGEMENT PLAN 2016**

BIOSECURITY AND AGRICULTURE MANAGEMENT ACT 2007**BIOSECURITY AND AGRICULTURE MANAGEMENT
(STABLE FLY) MANAGEMENT PLAN 2016**

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BIOSECURITY AND AGRICULTURE MANAGEMENT ACT 2007

**BIOSECURITY AND AGRICULTURE MANAGEMENT
(STABLE FLY) MANAGEMENT PLAN 2016**

Issued by the Minister under section 45 of the Act.

1. Citation

This management plan is the *Biosecurity and Agriculture Management (Stable Fly) Management Plan 2016*.

2. Commencement

This management plan comes into operation as follows—

- (a) clauses 1 and 2—on the day on which this management plan is published in the *Gazette*;
- (b) the rest of the management plan on the day after publication in the *Gazette*.—

3. Terms used

In this management plan—

approved measure means a measure that—

- (a) is approved by the Director General for the control of stable fly; and
- (b) is published on the department's electronic site.

approved pesticide means a chemical product that—

- (a) is effective for use in the control of Stable fly; and
- (b) is approved by, and registered with, the APVMA;

APVMA means the Australian Pesticides and Veterinary Medicines Authority continued by the *Agricultural and Veterinary Chemicals (Administration) Act 1992* (Commonwealth);

poultry means chickens, ducks, emus, geese, ostriches, turkeys, waterfowl and any other birds bred or kept for commercial purposes (other than for the purpose of sale as pets);

relevant land means land in an area described or set out in clause 4;

Stable fly means *Stomoxys calcitrans*.

4. Area to which management plan relates

This management plan relates to the areas of the State for which Stablefly is a declared pest¹.

5. Purpose of management plan

The purpose of this management plan is to provide for the control of Stable fly in each area to which this management plan relates.

6. Measures to be followed under management plan

The measures set out in clauses 7 to 10 are—

- (a) the prescribed control measures to control Stable fly to be taken, under section 30(2) of the Act, by the owner or other person in control, in an area for which Stable fly is a declared pest, of an organism or thing infested with Stable fly; and
- (b) the prescribed control measures to control Stable fly to be taken, under section 30(3) of the Act, by the owner or occupier of land in an area for which Stable fly is a declared pest, or a person who is conducting an activity on the land; and
- (c) the measures to be taken by a person who is directed under a pest control notice under section 31(1) of the Act to take the measures to control Stable fly required under this management plan.

7. Storage, use and transportation of commercially derived untreated poultry manure

(1) In this clause—

commercially derived untreated poultry manure means poultry manure, whether or not mixed with other materials, that—

- (a) is the result of a commercial poultry undertaking, including egg production through layer farming and meat production through broiler farming; and

¹ At the time of issue, this Management Plan relates to the Cities of Armadale, Cockburn, Joondalup, Kwinana, Rockingham, Swan and Wanneroo; the Shires of Capel, Chittering, Gingin, Harvey, Kalamunda and Sepentine-Jarrahdale; and the portion of the Shire of Murray described as the Harvey Coastal Plain Catchment State Planning Policy No. 2.

- (b) has not been treated by composting to the current Australian Standard 4454 or by means of an approved measure.
- (2) Commercially derived untreated poultry manure must not—
- (a) be stored or used on relevant land that is used for an agricultural activity; or
 - (b) be transported into or within an area to which this management plan relates
- unless with the prior approval of the Director General.
- (3) Subclause (2) does not apply to—
- (a) the storage of commercially derived untreated poultry manure at the place where it is produced for the purpose of composting to the current Australian Standard 4454 or treating the manure by means of an approved measure; or
 - (b) the temporary storage of commercially derived untreated poultry manure, at the place where it is produced, that is to be transported to—
 - (i) relevant land that is not used for an agricultural activity; or
 - (ii) an area to which this management plan does not relate; or
 - (c) the transportation of commercially derived untreated poultry manure to—
 - (i) relevant land that is not used for an agricultural activity; or
 - (ii) an area to which this management plan does not relate.

8. Cultivation and harvesting of annual fruits and certain vegetables

- (1) In this clause—
- fruit** does not include tomatoes or perennial fruits;
- vegetables** does not include—
- (a) beans; or
 - (b) capsicums (except paprikas); or
 - (c) cucumbers; or
 - (d) parsley; or
 - (e) potatoes; or
 - (f) spinach.
- (2) The measures set out in this clause apply to the commercial cultivation of fruit or vegetables on relevant land.
- (3) A crop of fruit or vegetables that has reached maturity must be either—
- (a) harvested as soon as is practicable for that type of fruit or vegetable; or
 - (b) as soon as is practicable, dealt with in accordance with subclauses (4) and (5) as if it had been completely harvested.
- (4) Within 3 days after a crop of fruit or vegetables has been harvested, any part of the crop that remains in or on the soil must be—
- (a) broken up into pieces with a high speed mulcher, flail mower or slasher (but not incorporated into the soil) and
 - (i) be treated with an approved pesticide; and
 - (ii) left undisturbed and unirrigated (except to the extent necessary to prevent wind erosion) for at least 7 days; and
 - (iii) after it has been left in accordance with paragraph (ii), be thoroughly incorporated into the soil with a rotary hoe or a similar device; or
 - (b) completely covered by more than 30cm of compacted soil by the means of appropriate machinery; or
 - (c) treated in accordance with an approved measure.
- (5) Fruit or vegetables that are not for human consumption, or are for any reason unsuitable for sale, must not remain on relevant land for more than 7 days after they are harvested unless they are
- (a) dealt with in accordance with subclause (4); or
 - (b) fed to stock in accordance with clause 10(2); or
 - (c) treated with an approved pesticide or by an approved measure and buried under at least 50 cm of soil.

9. Olive pressing

- (1) In this clause—
- olive pomace** means the residue left after pressing olives for olive oil.
- (2) Olive pomace must not be placed on relevant land unless the olive pomace is—
- (a) monitored at intervals of not less than 14 days for the presence of Stable fly; and
 - (b) unless dealt with in accordance with subclause (3), treated with an approved pesticide within 30 days of being placed on the land.
- (3) Any olive pomace on relevant land that is found to be infested with Stable fly must be immediately—
- (a) treated with an approved pesticide; and
 - (b) buried under at least 30 cm of soil.

10. Keeping stock

(1) The measures set out in this clause apply to the keeping of stock for commercial purposes on relevant land, including the operation of a feedlot on relevant land.

(2) Fruit or vegetables must not be fed to stock except—

- (a) in a trough; or
- (b) by being spread thinly on the ground.

(3) Any animal manure, soiled straw animal bedding, poultry litter or spilled grain feed that accumulates in an enclosure where stock are kept, and is not infested with Stable fly or Stable fly larvae, must be either—

- (a) monitored at intervals of not less than 7 days for the presence of Stable fly; or
- (b) dealt with in accordance with subclause (4) as if it were infested with Stable fly.

(4) Any animal manure, straw animal bedding, poultry litter or spilled grain feed on relevant land that is infested with Stable fly must immediately—

- (a) be collected into a heap or mound; and
- (b) be treated with an approved pesticide and left undisturbed for two weeks; or
- (c) be covered completely with plastic sheeting, and be kept covered until such time that it is not infested with Stable fly.

11. Repeal

(1) The *Biosecurity and Agriculture Management (Stable Fly) Management Plan 2013*, published in the *Gazette* on 5 July 2013 is repealed.

D. NALDER, Minister for Agriculture and Food.

Date 17 August 2016.

TRAINING MANUAL

STABLE FLY

This Manual is a Resource for:

- State and Local government Compliance officers that implement the '*Biosecurity and Agricultural Management (Stable Fly) Management Plan 2013*' for minimising stable fly development.
- Horticultural and Livestock producers affected by stable fly outbreaks or compliance with the *Stable Fly Management Plan 2016*

Author: Dr David Cook, DAFWA and University of Western Australia

V3. 2016

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BACKGROUND INFORMATION ON STABLE FLY

The stable fly, *Stomoxys calcitrans* (Diptera: Muscidae) has become an increasingly serious pest to the beef cattle and horse industries around Perth and extending out into traditional livestock areas along the Swan Coastal Plain, which is a 30km wide strip of sandy soils between the Indian Ocean and the Darling Scarp running from Lancelin (130km north of Perth) to Cape Naturaliste (260km south of Perth). *S. calcitrans* is a worldwide pest of livestock and humans that was first described in 1756 as a pest of livestock in mainly tropical regions; this fly is highly synanthropic (associated with human activities) and has followed the expansion of domestic animals and human settlements into more temperate regions of the world. The stable fly is of Afro-tropical origin and was first recorded in Australia in 1881, but not in Western Australia until 1912. Today it is common throughout subtropical and temperate Australia, generally in association with human settlement and wherever livestock are housed and fed.

The severity of the stable fly problem around Perth has been ongoing and escalating since the mid 1990's with no relief in sight for livestock producers, owners and rural residents alike. It is no coincidence that the stable fly problem has continued to escalate with the expansion and movement of large scale, vegetable production into traditional livestock areas on the Swan Coastal Plain. Complaints concerning flies from the general public include both themselves and their family pets and animals being harassed, attacked and bitten by flies. As a consequence people have had to adjust their lifestyles and are often unable to conduct social activities in their own backyards, go to local beaches where the stable flies often accumulate with the prevailing easterly winds over summer.

The stable flies' success as a pest species is due to its high degree of adaptability as it can develop in almost any accumulation of decaying vegetable matter with a high degree of bacterial activity, ageing animal manures or combination of manure and vegetable matter. In addition the larvae can tolerate very high temperatures (55-60°C black sands, silage pits). Management of larval habitats by sanitation is the key to stable fly control.

Figure 1. An adult stable fly (*S. calcitrans*) with prominent, biting mouthpart (L) (Photo courtesy of Pia Scanlon, DAFWA). Female flies can nearly triple their bodyweight after completing a blood meal (R).

Figure 2. Stable fly piercing mouthpart (Left & Centre) and an adult female drawing blood from a human.

This fly's prominent, piercing mouthpart is lowered and used to pierce the skin of animals and humans to draw blood, as is shown in the 3 pictures in Figure 2 (above).

PEST STATUS OF STABLE FLY

The name “stable fly” is an historical name given to the fly when it was first named in 1756. This fly first became a pest on livestock in the northern hemisphere with the housing of animals over winter in stables. Unable to change the straw bedding for months on end, it then became soiled with manure and urine and allowed for the “stable fly” to develop. The name “stable fly” suggests this fly only develops from animal stables, which is simply not the case in and around Perth. Horse stables rarely produce high numbers of stable flies as their manure is removed daily and horse manure is too dry for this fly to develop in. Other common names for this fly include biting house fly, dog fly, power mower fly and barn fly.

S. calcitrans is a worldwide pest of livestock, humans and wildlife across North and South America, Europe, Africa and more recently Australia. Intensive livestock industries (especially dairy cattle and cattle feedlots) in the US and parts of Europe have ongoing problems with this pest. The economic impact of stable flies on livestock production (in the US) is estimated at >\$2 billion per annum (dairy industry, pasture cattle, feedlot cattle) due to reduced milk production in dairy cows, decreased weight gain in beef cattle, and lowered feed efficiency. Stable flies are a major pest in Costa Rica with pineapple harvesting and in Brazil with sugar cane production where crop residues allow the fly to breed in huge numbers. The stable fly situation in and around Perth is unique due to the combination of our hot climate, porous sandy soils (that favour larval and pupal survival), close proximity of horticulture and livestock industries and overhead irrigation of vegetable crops (soil constantly moist, which promotes larval survival). Stable flies are typically only a seasonal problem in Queensland, New South Wales and Tasmania in association with cattle feedlots.

STABLE FLY IMPACT ON LIVESTOCK

Stable flies need to acquire blood from animals, and their main hosts are cattle and horses, with lesser hosts including humans, dogs, pigs, sheep (especially newborn lambs) and kangaroos. Stable flies are persistent biters, feeding several times a day, typically in early morning and late afternoon; the fly punctures the skin several times before drawing blood and their bite causes a sharp pain as it quickly draws blood and engorges itself in a few minutes. Female stable flies must feed on blood before being able to lay eggs, which they do in either rotting vegetable matter either alone or in combination with animal manures and urine.

Bites to livestock occur mainly on the limbs and belly and because animals react to their annoying bite, their feeding is often interrupted, hence there is an increased chance that the flies will move and feed on another animal, and hence have the opportunity to transmit pathogens. *Stomoxys calcitrans* can potentially transmit a number of diseases to livestock and to a lesser extent humans as well as being the intermediate hosts of

several species of nematode worms, which affect cattle and horses. When attempting to blood feed, stable flies often punctures the skin several times before drawing blood. Because animals react to their annoying bite, their feeding is often interrupted, hence there is an increased chance that the flies will move and feed on another animal, and hence have the opportunity to transmit pathogens.

Stableflies and houseflies have been implicated in the transmission of a range of diseases, which affect human and livestock. Disease organisms can either be transmitted mechanically (disease particles adhere to the flies mouthparts after feeding and/or their outer cuticle) or many hairs, or (ii) by remaining viable in the flies crop (pre-stomach) and gut where the organism is regurgitated in subsequent feeding bouts. Some diseases can remain in the fly for a considerable time and be capable of being transmitted to uninfected hosts. For example, a strain of Streptococcal bacteria can be transmitted by the stable fly for up to 14 days following an infective meal. Certain diseases can persist in the larval stage of the fly, through the dormant pupal phase and still remain infective in feeding by the emerging adult fly. On the other hand some disease organisms only have a short period of survival (only 3 hours in the case of Potomac horse fever), in particular when they are adhered to the mouthparts of the fly itself as opposed to being ingested into the crop of the fly. The table below lists diseases of humans and livestock that have been linked with stable flies in either field or laboratory experiments (those diseases that occur in Australia are indicated with an asterisk).

Table 1. Diseases of humans and livestock whose transmission has been implicated by stable flies in either field or laboratory experiments (*= diseases that occur in Australia).

LIVESTOCK	HUMANS
Eperythrozoon suis (swine) *	Streptococcal*
Equine Infectious Anemia *	Enterobacter*
Pink Eye*	Rift Valley Fever
Pasteurellosis*	Amoebic Dysentery*
Brucellosis*	Helminths*
Bovine Mastitis*	HIV*
Anthrax*	Anthrax*
Arbovirus	Leprosy
African Horse Sickness	Recurrent Fever
Surra	Yaws
Rinderpest	
West Nile Virus	
Swine Fever	
Lumpy Skin Disease	
Campylobacteriosis	

Figure 3. A typical reaction in horses to continual bites from the biting fly- the bites come up in welts, which are extremely itchy and horses will often have an allergic reaction to them.

Figure 4. Horses often react violently to stable flies and try to repel them by rolling in the sand, stamping their feet and tossing their head.

Figure 5. Cattle affected by stable flies typically flick sand on themselves in an effort to dislodge the flies, in particular bulls, which are often isolated and come under serious attack by the fly. Individual cattle have been seen with well over 100 stable flies on them, well above the economic threshold of 20 flies/animal.

Figure 6. Cattle being affected by biting flies typically bunch together and move around in a circle, tossing up sand onto themselves in order to lessen the chances of a stable fly landing on them and biting them, which in hot summer conditions causes heat stress and loss of condition in the cattle.

As few as only 20 adult stable flies per animal can reduce daily weight gain and disrupt marketing plans in cattle (Catangui et al. 1993, Campbell et al. 2001). When attacked by stable flies, cattle bunch together and their efforts to repel the flies lead to heat stress and reduced feeding (Catangui et al. 1997, Mullens et al. 2006, Wieman et al. 1992). Severe outbreaks of this fly have resulted in animal deaths in large ungulates (Elkan et al. 2009). Outbreaks of this pest fly have forced cattle and horse owners to relocate their animals away from affected areas. In addition, human lifestyle has been seriously affected in rural residential areas (Cook et al. 1999) with recreational activities and outdoor living severely curtailed.

Just looking at the economic losses to cattle owners, this includes lost meat production gains, reduced calving, control the stable fly (mostly insecticidal), and for horse owners there are costs for protective clothing, insecticides, fly repellents, veterinary fees, traps, agistment fees etc. Rural residents are affected financially by paying for fly control costs (fly baits, traps, repellents, protective clothing, dog and pet fly control, veterinary fees, flyscreen mesh, purpose built enclosures etc), reduced value of real estate and loss of tourism in warmer months in the coastal towns of around Lancelin & Guilderton.

Figure 7. Protective clothing for horses against stable fly and family pets (dogs) affected by stable fly.

GENERALISED FLY LIFE CYCLE

Flies are an example of a holometabolous insect where they undergo complete metamorphosis. In other words, the immature larval stage has no resemblance to the adult form. During the pupal phase (cocoon or chrysalis), the larva undergoes metamorphosis and changes into the adult fly.

The life cycle of a fly (see above) consists of eggs, larvae (3 instars or growth phases), pupal (dormant) and finally the adult fly. The larvae are the intense feeding phase where the amount and quality of food they ingest largely determines the size of the resultant adult fly. Once an adult fly has emerged, it cannot increase in size at all by feeding further; their size as an adult is fixed (due to their hard, exoskeleton).

Both the egg and larval stages are highly susceptible to desiccation and require moist conditions to survive. The egg stage lasts ≈ 24 hrs before the first larval instar emerges and commences feeding. The larvae feed and moult through 3 instars before the final larval stages leaves or wanders from the food source in search of drier soil in order to form a pupae.

Figure 8. Fly eggs are typically laid in discrete masses (L), which hatch into the larval feeding phase (R).

Figure 9. After feeding is complete, fly larvae pupate (L) from which the adult fly eventually emerges (R).

The pupal phase remains dormant in the soil for anywhere from 1-2 weeks up to several months (depending upon soil temperature) before the adult fly emerges from the pupal case (see figure 9 above), and digs its way to the soil surface. Once emerged, the adult fly remains on the ground for several hours waiting for its outer cuticle to harden and the wings to become firm and ready to fly. It is important to note, that stable flies (as with most flies) are unable to dig back down into soil once they have dug their way up and emerged onto the soil surface.

Figure 10. The final wandering phase of fly larvae (top L) progressing to the pupal phase. The pupal case hardens and darkens with age to dark red/black just prior to adult fly emergence (bottom L). After emerging from the pupae, the spent pupal cases can be found in soil indicating the adult fly has already emerged (R).

Flies are reliant on the outside temperature for their development, i.e. they cannot generate heat by themselves. That is why below about 15°C flies typically don't fly as there is not enough heat to warm up the flight muscles in their thorax. The graph below shows the impact temperature has on the development rate of stable fly larvae. At 32°C, it takes 2 weeks to complete larval development (from 1st to 3rd instar), whereas in the cooler winter temperatures of 15-18°C, it takes >7 weeks to complete larval development. Similarly, the length of the dormant, pupal phase is influenced by the soil temperature, where development can be as short as 5-6 days at around 30-35°C (but with reduced % survival) and up to over 30 days at 15°C.

Figure 11. Larval development time for *Stomoxys calcitrans* as a function of temperature (Lysk 1998).

Figure 12. The duration of development from egg to adult emergence in *S. calcitrans* against temperature (Kunz et al. 1977).

Total development (from egg to adult emergence) can take over 4 weeks at around 20° but take half as long at temperatures of 30°C and above (see figure 11 above).

STABLE FLY LIFE HISTORY STAGES

All the life history stages of stable fly (eggs, larvae (3 instar stages), pupae (dormant phase in soil), spent pupae (adult flies already emerged) that may be either under near or away from the original food source that the larvae fed on) and be able to identify them in rotting vegetable waste, animal manures, combinations of the two and any other rotting putrescible waste of plant origin (eg olive pressing pumace, wet piles of lawn clippings, rotting vegetable produce such as reject eggplants and rockmelons).

Females typically lay eggs in scattered groups of 15-20 and lay a total of around 90 eggs in each complete ovarian cycle. They then feed a further two more times on blood before being able to develop the next batch of eggs, of which the protein from the bloodmeal is used to produce.

Figure 13. The life history stages of the stable or biting fly *Stomoxys calcitrans*.

The first instar larvae are just over 1mm when they first hatch from the eggs. By the time they are 2.5mm long they moult to the second instar stage (2.5 - 4.5mm) and the third instar larvae range from 5mm to a maximum of 12-14mm long.

Figure 14. Scattered stable fly eggs on rotting carrot tops (L) and larvae in rotting cauliflower residues (R).

Stable fly larvae need a moist environment to survive and are equipped with a pair of Keilin's organs on each of their three thoracic segments (Friesen *et al.* 2015). Keilin's organs are trichoid sensilla that serve as hygrometers (Hafez 1950), indicating that larvae can detect and orient with respect to moisture levels.

IDENTIFYING ADULT STABLE FLIES

Adult Stable flies are slightly smaller in size than a house fly, but with an obvious biting mouthpart sticking out from their head. Their abdomen has a typical checkerboard appearance and the thorax has two pairs of parallel black lines converging at the front of the thorax (see Figure 15 below).

The flies love to rest on a cool, vertical white surface and are often seen clustered on the sides of white vehicles. They have a distinct resting posture in a heads up position, at about a 30° from the parallel. This is in contrast to most flies which rest with their wings virtually parallel with the ground/surface. In addition, their wings are held out at about a 45° angle and not at about 20-30° in most other nuisance fly species.

Figure 15. Top view of the dorsal surface of stable fly (L) versus house fly (*Musca domestica*) (R).

Figure 16. The typical size of adult stable flies relative to bush flies and house flies.

The easiest way to identify a stable fly is to look from side on and see the prominent black biting proboscis of the fly, which looks like a thin needle pointing straight ahead when at rest, or points down when lowered to draw blood from its host (see Figure 17 below).

Figure 17. The mouthparts of a stable fly (L) versus house fly (*Musca domestica*) (R).

Figure 18. An adult stable fly, *Stomoxys calcitrans* (front on view) (L) and side view (R).

STABLE FLY BLOOD FEEDING

Both sexes of stable fly adults are obligate haematophages (they must feed on blood) and have significant medical and economic impact through annoyance, production losses and potential disease transmission amongst mammals. Both sexes blood feed twice per day, ingesting around 26mg of blood with each blood meal. An electronic bitometer was used to study the feeding activity of adult stablefly and showed that females averaged 1.8 feeds/day, and males averaged 2.8 feeds/day. Stable flies have a high preference for cattle and horses, followed to a lesser degree by humans, especially where cattle and horses aren't available.

Figure 19. Stable flies actively feeding on a pelican infected with West Nile virus (photo by Greg Johnson, Montana State University, US)

Females blood feed for up to 5 days (twice/day) before laying their first batch of eggs. Between laying of batches of eggs a female requires at least 2-3 more blood meals. The amount of blood ingested daily by the males is relatively constant as males don't need to sequester nutrients for reproduction as do females. Females typically lay up to about 90-100 eggs in total over about 4-5 deposition sites, scattering 15-20 eggs at each site. Females mate at 1 day after emergence and males at 2 days after emergence. Females only require one mating to lay eggs over their lifetime. In the peak of summer, adult stable flies typically live no more than 2 weeks, whereas flies emerging in cooler autumn and spring months will survive up to about 4 weeks. Flies developing over winter can survive as adult flies for the longest time of around 6 weeks.

Figure 20. Several hundred stable flies on a bull (L) and stable flies feeding on a horse's leg (R).

STABLE FLY DISPERSAL

Adult stable flies typically disperse anywhere from 2 – 20km after emergence, with over 50% of newly emerged stable flies dispersing beyond 1.6 km of their natal site. Only a small percentage of around 5% disperse beyond 5 km (Taylor et al. 2010). These results indicate that stable fly adults on cattle in a given area are most likely to have originated from larval development sites within a 5 km radius of the subject cattle. The adult fly emerges before sunrise and after an hour or so allowing their cuticle to harden and veins in their wings to inflate with haemolymph (insect blood), they then travel with the prevailing winds

(easy ride). After locating suitable livestock hosts, their movement shortens considerably, and they typically move 0.5-1.5km over 48 hours thereafter if their hosts remain in the same area (Pitzer et al. 2011; Showler & Osbrink 2015).

OTHER NUISANCE FLIES

Many people often confuse several other common nuisance flies with the biting or stable fly. The biting fly is very similar in size and appearance to both the common house fly (*Musca domestica*) and the bush fly (*Musca vetustissima*). The major difference between these flies is that the biting fly has, as their name suggests, a prominent biting mouthpart. Stable flies are persistent biters, feeding on animals several times a day, preferring to bite cattle and horses, but will also attack humans, dogs, pigs, newborn lambs, pet kangaroos and emus. The typical influx of bush flies every spring in and around Perth around mid October sees a dramatic increase in flies and nuisance to both humans and livestock. The bush fly is an obligate dung breeder, so it will not breed in any other resource except animal dung, and typically cattle dung. The bush flies persist in large numbers until usually just after Christmas/New Year when they follow the senescing pastures further south with the prevailing easterly winds.

Figure 21. Bush flies (*Musca vetustissima*) feeding on fresh cattle dung (L) and house flies (*Musca domestica*), which can breed in a range of animal manures and rotting vegetable matter.

The populations of bush flies that plague Perth and surrounding areas every late spring through summer are often confused with the stable fly. In fact one of the recognized common names for *S. calcitrans* is the “biting house fly”, which is quite an apt description of this fly as it is of similar size to the house fly, but with a prominent, biting mouthpart.

STABLE FLY BREEDING SOURCES

MAJOR SOURCES

1. VEGETABLE CROP RESIDUE LEFT AFTER HARVEST

Vegetable crop residues left after harvesting was complete are the most significant source of stable fly development on the Swan Coastal Plain. Given that raw poultry manure is no longer available for use by commercial growers, then vegetable crop residues remaining after harvest, namely, (i) stalks, leaves and fruit left on the ground after harvesting) and ii) harvested crop waste (i.e., damaged and rejected produce) remain the greatest challenge to stable fly management. .

Figure 22. Rotting leaves and stalks left after harvest from leafy crops such as cauliflower (LHS) and celery (RHS) allow biting flies to develop in huge numbers on soils that are regularly watered overhead.

Figure 23. The huge amount of leaves and stalks and reject produce left after harvesting is complete in crop such as cabbage (left) and silverbeet (right) provide a perfect breeding ground for biting flies.

Samples collected from commercial vegetable growers have shown that over 1,000 stable flies/m² can emerge from the soil of a trashed vegetable crop. Typically, one to several hundred stable flies develop from the rotting residue of broccoli, cabbage, cauliflower, celery and lettuce crops - the sheer amount of vegetable matter on the ground represents a significant potential risk for stable fly breeding if it is left to rot for more than 3-4 days and/or is simply rotary hoed into the soil with minimal physical breakdown.

Breaking down vegetable crop residue down into small pieces, will significantly reduce and even prevent stable fly breeding and have the added benefit of allowing growers to put another crop in that area sooner and reduce the risk of disease transmission to the next crop. The vegetable crops that support stable fly development when residues of the crops are left to rot after harvest include: beetroot, broccoli, cabbage, cauliflower, celery, chinese radish, coriander, corn, leek, lettuce, silverbeet, spring onions and squashes.

2. REJECT AND/OR DAMAGED PRODUCE

Many vegetable and fruit crops that are regularly harvested over an extended period of time (weeks to months) result in reject and/or damaged produce being left on the ground either under the crop vines or in the space between rows of the crop. This is often the case with crop such as eggplants (aubergines), rockmelons, watermelons, snow peas, sugar snap peas, paprikas (bell peppers), capsicums, carrots and zucchinis. Produce either rejected within the vegetable/fruit crop or at first stage processing and/or sorting are all capable of supporting the development of biting flies and other nuisance flies if not handled properly. There are several outstanding examples of this in Shires around Perth, including (i) the disposal of large quantities of carrots rejected for export into open pits; (ii) egg plants and paprikas rejected for market are simply left to rot underneath and between the plants (see figures below); (iii) large areas of both rockmelon and watermelon were left with numerous melons that were rejected for harvest.

Figure 24. Reject and/or damaged produce such as eggplant (L) and Chinese radish (R) provide an ideal place for biting flies to develop in.

Figure 25. Reject produce of both capsicum (L) and eggplant (R) allow fly breeding to occur, however stable flies rarely develop from rotting capsicums, whereas eggplants produce 13 stable flies/rotten fruit.

As many of these crops are picked over several months, they can allow stable flies to breed over weeks to months as reject produce accumulates under the crop. Reject produce must be either (i) physically removed, put into an open pit and deep buried weekly with at least 30 cm of soil; or (ii) sprayed weekly with a high volume pesticide application. The cost to growers of physically removing reject produce was seen as being prohibitive, but they are willing to spray the crop at least once weekly for other insect pests and assume that this spray application would control any stable fly larvae developing in the rotting fruit.

Figure 26. Reject and/or damaged produce such as pumpkins (L) and paprikas (bell peppers) (R) that are left on the ground, ultimately rot and allow fly breeding to occur.

Figure 27. Stable fly larvae feeding in rotting paprikas (L) and pumpkins (R) indicated by black arrows.

Figure 28. Reject and/or damaged produce such as rockmelons left on the ground to rot support stable fly development, where the melons are picked over several months and reject produce accumulate.

Figure 29. Dumping of reject and/or damaged produce such as carrots, spring onions (L) and eggplants (R) into large piles can allow for fly breeding to occur over weeks to months.

Figure 30. Large scale dumping of reject produce such as carrots (bottom left and right) can have dire consequences if not managed properly. Weekly pesticide applications can prevent fly breeding.

Reject produce that represent the highest risk of producing stable flies are eggplants, rockmelons and paprikas, where >10 stable flies develop from each fruit, and to a lesser extent pumpkins and zucchinis.

Figure 31. Reject produce such as broccoli heads (L) and paprikas (R) in large piles produce stable flies.

Samples of reject cucumbers, cherry tomatoes, chilli peppers or potatoes **did not support stable fly development**, whilst capsicums and tomatoes rarely produced stable flies (<0.5 stable flies/fruit). Reject produce that did produce stable flies included broccoli heads, carrots, Chinese radish, eggplants, paprikas, pumpkins, rockmelons, snow peas, sugar snap peas, turnips, zucchinis and watermelons.

3. REJECT VEGETABLES FED OUT TO LIVESTOCK

Several livestock owners (mostly cattle growers) were found to have fed out excessive amounts of reject carrots (predominantly), cauliflowers and broccoli to cattle (and to a lesser extent horses) as supplementary feed during the hot, summer months when pasture and hay was scarce. When this organic material is left in a large pile/heap, much of the material is trampled on by the cattle as they feed. This, along with the fact that the animals defecate and urinate on the material, means that all the vegetables are invariably not eaten.

Figure 32. Dark stained area in sandy paddocks where reject vegetables had been fed out to cattle.

Figure 33. Cattle feeding on piles of reject carrots (L) and a close-up of the reject carrots.

Figure 34. Reject corn cobs and leaves fed out to cattle in large piles ferment and generate heat that accelerates larval development.

This mixture of vegetable matter and animal manure/urine then ultimately rots on the ground. It may take several weeks and even up to a month for this vegetable matter to breakdown to the point where it is attractive to stable flies, but the resultant mixture of rotting vegetables, manure and urine presents an ideal environment for nuisance fly and stable fly breeding to occur. Flies recovered from reject vegetables fed out to cattle included the stable fly and other nuisance flies including house fly, blue-bodied blowfly, black carrion fly, false stable fly and cheese skippers. Stable flies can tolerate very high soil: organic matter and/or animal manure ratios (Hogsette 1996) and what appears to be merely soiled sand with animal manure and/or rotting organic matter can be a highly suitable environment for stable flies to develop.

When feeding reject vegetables to cattle, the vegetables should be placed in a long, thin line to allow cattle easy access to the food and avoid trampling and rotting of excess material mixed in combination with the animal's dung and urine (see figures below). Feeding out of reject lettuce, corn cobs, broccoli, silverbeet, carrots, spring onions and onions has resulted in the development of stable flies.

Figure 35. Feeding out of market reject vegetables to livestock should be done so in long, thin lines to ensure that excess vegetable matter isn't left behind to rot and enable stable flies to develop.

4. CATTLE FEEDLOTS

Housing large numbers of animals in a small area inevitably runs the risk of manure accumulation and potential fly breeding. Cattle held in a feedlot situation can produce stable flies if either (i) their manure gets wet either through leaking water troughs or poor drainage around where manure accumulates; or (ii) there are spilled areas or wet areas of grain feed, which rot and ferment and attract stable flies.

Fresh cattle dung (0-7d old) is highly attractive to bush flies, which are obligate dung breeders. However, as the dung ages beyond 3 weeks, it is utilized by stable flies. In a normal paddock situation, cattle dung rarely gets this old due to dung beetle activity and the rapid drying out of the dung in our hot climate. However, large-scale feedlotting of cattle prior to sale or export means that a huge amount of cattle dung is produced in a very small area. If this dung remains moist and/or their grain feed becomes moist and is mixed with the dung then this can support the development of nuisance flies including stable flies. Overflowing water troughs and dung accumulation in pens was demonstrated to produce stable flies in cattle yards and feedlots.

Figure 36. Large accumulation of cattle dung in pens attract flies, who quickly lay eggs on the material (L) and within 7-10 days have formed into hard, pupal cases (R) from which the adult flies emerge.

Figure 37. Cattle feedlots produce vast amounts of animal manure where large amounts can accumulate.

Figure 38. Cattle feedlots where grain and straw feed mix left uneaten is left to rot in the bottom of feed troughs (L) attract large numbers of flies (R), which are able to support stable fly development.

5. ROTTING HAY RESIDUES

The residues of hay fed out to livestock over the dry summer months can later represent a significant risk for stable fly development with rainfall and warm autumn and winter temperatures. It may take months for excess hay mixed in with animal manure and urine to rot and present a suitable breeding site for stable flies. Hay residues can either be under and around hay feeders, in cattle yards, feedlot situations or in particular places around the paddocks where hay bales/rolls are fed out to cattle.

Livestock producers need to be mindful of this situation where they could be inadvertently producing stable flies that are affecting their own animals and others nearby. If fly larvae are found in this material, spreading out thinly or scarifying will NOT kill the fly larvae – the larvae in the affected areas must be either (i) deep buried to a depth of at least 1m, or (ii) sprayed with a pesticide and left undisturbed to allow any emerging flies to contact the chemical residue/barrier. The best way to manage hay residues is to be aware of when livestock have finished feeding on the hay and then spread the material out thinly to dry it out and prevent it from decomposing and fermenting when it gets wet due to any rainfall events.

Figure 39. Bales of hay exposed to the weather (L) and large areas where hay has been fed out to livestock (R) can take months to rot when wet, providing an ideal place for stable flies to develop.

Figure 40. Moisture accumulates at the bottom of the hay bales (L) and removal of the top layer reveals actively feeding stable fly larvae and a single pupae on the right hand side of the image (R).

6. RAW POULTRY MANURE

Although raw poultry manure has been banned since September 2011 for application onto the soil as a fertilizer in irrigated horticulture within the 13 designated Shires around Perth, there remains the temptation for growers to take the risk of receiving delivery of raw poultry manure (broiler litter and egg layer manure) for use in their crop production. Similarly, the market now has a lot of composted and/or conditioned manure-based products that growers are moving over to in place of raw poultry manure.

Figure 41. Deliveries of raw poultry manure (LHS) can result in house and stable fly development if the manure is delivered either wet and/or the manure becomes wet from sprinkler overspray or rain events.

Amended poultry manure based products, soil conditioners and/or compost products have the potential to breed significant numbers of flies if not processed properly and/or are left in a damp condition for extended period of time. These products must have their production process approved by the WA Health Department and have had samples tested for levels of fly breeding, where there must be a >90% reduction in fly breeding relative to raw poultry litter. Poultry broiler litter stacks that are left to age in the field represent the highest risk for stable fly breeding if they get wet (irrigation, rainfall event), whereas egg layer manure (without an organic matter base) are a significantly less risk of producing stable flies.

Flies respond to variations in the physical and chemical properties of manure, where larval survival correlates with levels of phosphorus and adult emergence correlates with moisture content (Barnard and Harms 1992). Brues (1946) speculated that differences in the pH of rotting materials was a major factor in determining the species of fly larvae found within the material. The author suggested that stable flies developed in acidic materials such as rotting straw or lawn clippings, whereas house flies preferred a more alkaline environment. Stable flies prefer to develop in a more aged and fermented poultry litter (>4-7 d old), whereas house flies did not use poultry litter that had aged for more than 9 days (see Figure 41 below). Similarly, house flies prefer fresh cattle manure as a larval breeding medium, whereas stable flies do not breed in the manure until it is at least 19 d old (Broce and Haas 1999).

Fig. 42. Numbers of stable flies and house flies emerging from poultry litter aged between 0 and 14 days (from Cook *et al.* 1999).

LESSER SOURCES OF STABLE FLY BREEDING

7. OLIVE PRESSING RESIDUE (POMACE)

The process of pressing olives leaves a pulp and seed residue that is simply pumped out onto the soil nearby to the processing plant, where it forms a “larval flow” appearance and is about 50-60cm thick. This material is quite acidic and fermented and has been found to contain significant numbers of fly larvae as the material is exposed to flies after processing and splits and dries forming a cracked and crazed surface that is ideal for flies to search and explore and lay eggs on the moist rotting organic material below. This is a standard method of disposal of the pulp residue across all processing sheds.

Figure 43. The process of pressing olives to extract oil produces a large amount of organic residue (seed, skin and pulp) called pomace, that is simply piped out onto the ground and left to dry (top left and right).

Figure 44. Olive pressing residue is spread on the ground for several months where as it dries out it leaves cracks and fissures (R) that flies find highly attractive to search for a place to lay their eggs.

Figure 45. Stable fly larvae feeding in olive pressing residue (L) and newly formed stable fly pupae (R).

8. ABANDONED CROPS

Vegetable/fruit crops can be abandoned due to either poor market prices, low quality fruit, problems with watering and/or fertilizer regimes, disease or adverse weather; the remaining fruit rot on the plants and/or drop off and rot on the ground.

Figure 46. Abandoned crops of baby aubergines (LHS) and roma tomatoes (RHS).

Figure 47. Abandoned aubergine fruit (LHS) and capsicums (RHS) left on the ground to rot following a decline in market value. These rotting fruit attract and support the development of stable flies.

Figure 48. Abandoned tomatoes left on the vine to rot rarely produce stable flies.

9. PIGGERIES

Piggeries are an intensive, animal industry that has an enormous amount of manure to dispose of on a daily basis. The standard method of disposal is to run the manure through a series of effluent ponds where microbial activity breaks down the manure over time till a substance “inert” to fly breeding is left. Unfortunately this process has revealed some serious misgivings in terms of fly breeding and if it goes wrong, the level of fly breeding can be astronomical.

Pigs housed in free range, eco-shelter facilities (see pictures below) may be kept in the straw-based enclosures for anything up to 3 months. As time progresses, the pig manure mixed with straw bedding in particular presents a great risk of breeding flies with the manure and organic content of the rotting straw (from urine soaking and water sprayers) mixing together.

Figure 49. Eco shelters with straw covered floors house pigs through their major growing phase (L and R).

Figure 50. Eco shelters with an accumulation of pig manure in the corners (left), which when mixed with the straw bedding provides an ideal place for flies to breed (right).

Piggeries attract huge numbers of flies due to their strong odour, but their ability to allow for fly breeding can be significantly reduced by having a Fly Management Plan in place involving trapping of adult flies, prevention of larval breeding sites (i.e. sanitation) and the use of insecticides on surfaces where flies rest.

Figure 51. Effluent ponds for the microbial decomposition of pig manure can malfunction and allow for the rapid accumulation of manure (left and right) and an enormous area for flies to develop.

Figure 52. Accumulated pig manure in effluent ponds allow for flies to develop as evidenced by hundreds of fly pupae under manure crusts (left) and along the sand bank above the black, plastic lining the ponds.

From the samples taken across several piggeries, stable flies were not seen to be produced in any significantly large numbers. House flies were the predominant nuisance fly that developed from the combination of samples of pig manure, manure and straw bedding and series of effluent ponds. The situations where biting flies were produced was when pig manure was mixed with sand (e.g. effluent pond edges where sand had built-up over time) or pig manure and straw bedding combined had been able to age for a significant amount of time after pen cleanout (several weeks).

10. SILAGE

Silage is grass or other green fodder compacted and stored under airtight conditions, typically in a silo or under a large tarpaulin, without first being dried, and used as animal feed in the winter. This ageing of the plant material makes it an “at risk” substrate for stable fly development. Skidmore (1985) cites regularly finding stable fly larvae in steaming or smouldering silage heaps, where very high temperatures are maintained by the bacterial and fungal activity.

Figure 53. A silage pit opened to feed cattle (L), but which allows for stable fly development (R) .

11. MISCELLANEOUS SOURCES OF STABLE FLY BREEDING

Fly larvae were also found in a range of situations (eg turf production, seedling production) as well as in wild melons, which allowed stable flies to develop in low numbers. Lawn clippings are only ever a problem in terms of breeding stable flies if they are stored in large piles that are continually allowed to get

wet. The sawdust base of potting substrate for seedling production, which when removed and put onto the ground (with roots and seed cotyledons in amongst the material) resulted in stable flies breeding. Sawdust (pine and jarrah) bases used in broiler bird meat production are the reason why broiler litter is such a high risk of producing stable flies as this organic matter is mixed with poultry manure. Rotting, wild pig melons from around processing sheds, dams and nearby bushland or on roadsides around Perth mostly produce beneficial hover flies (Syrphidae), which are pollinators of many native flowering plants.

Figure 54. Rotting wild melons (pig) produce mainly hover flies (Syrphidae), which are beneficial pollinators of native plants, but also allow for stable flies to develop in low numbers.

Figure 55. Turf farms typically leave the cut grass on the surface to dry out and blow away (L), but if the clippings are left in piles that get regularly wet (R), they will produce stable flies.

Figure 56. Accumulations of sawdust potting base (L) or seedling roots, cotyledons and potting mix placed in piles on pasture (R) can result in stable fly breeding.

ASSESSING LEVELS OF STABLE FLY BREEDING

By breeding, we mean the presence of the stable fly larval and/or pupal stages. Larvae go through 3 larval instars; the smallest 1st instar larvae are just over 1mm when they first hatch from eggs. At 2.5mm long they moult to the 2nd instar stage (2.5 - 4.5mm) and 3rd instar larvae range from 5mm up to 12-14mm long.

In determining the level of stable fly breeding on a property, there has to be some count done on the numbers of stable fly larvae and/or pupae in a given area, along with gathering the following information:

- (i) the size of the property
- (ii) the proportion of the property where stable fly larvae/pupae are found
- (iii) the density of stable fly larvae/pupae in that resource (number per sample or per square meter)
the likely numbers of adult stable flies that will result/have already emerged from that resource
eg a few larvae every sample spread out over 5,000m² can easily produce >100,000 stable flies, which is far more serious than one obvious pile of rotting material with a few hundred larvae
- (iv) is it an on-going problem or a one-off situation (machinery breakdown, manager away, weather conditions, accidental spillage, abandoned crop due to disease or market price fall, etc).

Figure 57. Stable fly eggs on rotting carrots in a reject produce pit (L) and stable fly larvae on the soil interface under rotting celery (R).

Figure 58. Stable fly larvae in rotting celery (L) and pupae under reject cabbages (R).

DEFINING A SAMPLING UNIT

When you have chosen an area to assess the level of stable fly breeding (i.e. presence of larvae and/or pupae), you must be consistent as possible with what you decide is your sampling unit.

- 1) If it is the post-harvest remains of a vegetable crop, then select discrete pieces of the rotting material that are visible at the soil surface. Use of a trowel helps in removing a consistent amount of vegetable matter and soil for inspection of fly larvae and/or pupae
- 2) If it is soiled straw/manure bedding material in a livestock facility then dig into the material with a trowel and count larvae and/or pupae over the area the trowel dug up.
- 3) If it is reject produce, then each piece of rotting fruit becomes the standard sampling unit and you simply count the number of stable fly larvae in each piece as well as inspect the soil underneath the rotting fruit for presence of stable fly larvae.

STABLE FLY BREEDING ASSESSMENT

The tables on the following pages will help you to make a determination and/or judgement on the level of stable fly breeding on a particular property/enterprise in each potential source of stable fly breeding.

The ultimate decision is based on all the factors (listed above) and there will always be an element of subjectivity as you simply cannot logistically sample every square meter of large, commercial enterprises.

To make your Stable Fly Breeding Assessment, follow the steps below:

1. Take 10 samples of material (likely to have stable fly) randomly across the area to assess
2. Place each sample onto a flat surface/tray/ice cream container and sort through quickly with your trowel, a pen, forceps or anything similar to quickly count the number of fly larvae/pupaea in each.
3. Record the number of fly larvae/pupae in each sample and determine a mean from the 10 samples
4. After calculating the mean, use the tables below to help determine the severity of stable fly breeding

Any assessment mean that is >5 stable fly larvae/pupae will automatically trigger some level of compliance (eg Letter of Advice, Pest Control Notice)

For an obvious, discrete resource (eg manure heap, pile of rotting vegetables, heap of lawn clippings, reject produce scattered through an existing crop)

Mean # of Stable Fly Larvae/Pupae per Sample	Rating of Stable Fly Breeding	Compliance
>20	EXTREME	✓
10-20	HIGH	✓
5-9	MEDIUM	✓
1-4	LOW	NIL

For a large, open area such as an entire vegetable crop bay (typically 15m wide by 250m long) or manure accumulated in a feedlot/paddock

Mean # of Stable Fly Larvae/Pupae per Sample	Rating of Stable Fly Breeding	Compliance
>10	EXTREME	✓
5-9	HIGH	✓
1-4	MEDIUM	NIL
0-1	LOW	NIL

FINDING STABLE FLY LARVAE IN THE FIELD

Stable fly larvae are quite uniformly thin, with a long thin narrowing of the front half of the maggot or larvae to the mouthparts. When disturbed or exposed to light, they will stop moving totally and feign death as an anti-predatory response. They can remain motionless for anywhere up to 30 seconds before they move again and seek soil or being able to hide underneath anything nearby that is in the dark. When they do move, they have a very characteristic method of doing so, with the front half of the maggot moving quickly from side to side like a windscreen wiper. Stable fly larvae are quite thin with the front half narrowing to very thin, pointy larval mouthparts (see Figure 57 overleaf).

Figure 59. Stable fly larvae in the field, underneath rotting celery (Top L); rotting, reject red cabbages (Top R), underneath rotting broccoli (Bottom L) and in reject corn cobs fed to livestock (Bottom R).

Figure 60. Fly larvae indicating front feeding end mouthparts (L) and posterior spiracles through which the larvae take in oxygen. Three posterior spiracle slits indicate the larvae is a third instar larvae.

Occasionally you will come across beetle larvae feeding on the decaying organic matter, in particular in rotting watermelons, rockmelons, eggplants, carrots and potatoes. Beetle larvae can be distinguished from fly larvae as they have a hard brown head capsule and 6 short prolegs at the front of the larvae in contrast to fly larvae that have no head capsule nor any prolegs (see Figure 61 below).

Figure 61. Fly larvae (L) compared with a beetle larvae (R) – note brown head capsule on beetle larvae.

FINDING STABLE FLY PUPAE IN THE FIELD

Stable fly pupae are quite small (2-5mm long) and start out almost red in colour and with ageing become red-brown to brown and finally dark-brown to almost black just prior to the adult stable fly emerging. So when you find stable fly pupae in the field, their colour will give you an indication of age and the likelihood of adult flies emerging soon. This dormant phase is when the larvae undergo complete metamorphosis and change from a larval form into the adult stable fly. The wandering larvae of stable fly do not travel far from their original larval food source, but typically they seek drier soil in which to pupate as it is far more difficult for them to lay down chitin (the protein component of insect cuticle and pupal casings) in moist to wet soils. So underneath any rotting organic matter and slightly out to the sides in a 5-10cm radius is as far as you will have to look for the small, brown grains of rice that the pupae resemble. In addition, they are never very deep in the soil, most are within the top 5cm and occasionally down as far as 10cm deep. Below are some real life examples of stable fly pupae in field situations.

Figure 62. Stable fly pupae in the field, underneath rotting, reject red cabbages (Left) and newly formed pupae (red) in olive pressing pomace (Right).

PRACTICAL TIPS

Some helpful practical tips on searching for fly larvae and in particular stable fly larvae in the field are:

- (i) expose material to sunlight wherever possible and look for larvae moving away from the light
- (ii) expose material in successive layers/partings and wait 5-10 secs looking for larval movement
- (iii) remember that stable fly larvae will feign death when first contacted for up to 30 secs
- (iv) stable fly larvae are often on the interface between the rotting vegetable matter and the soil
- (v) look down and inside rotting vegetable root stump (stem base) for stable fly larvae
- (vi) search soil directly beneath rotting organic matter for presence of stable fly pupae
- (vii) do successive shallow scrapings of the soil with a trowel/knife to find stable fly pupae
- (viii) only scrape through soil down to a depth of 5-10cm and laterally to the same distance

In assessing stable fly breeding severity, also determine the chronology of vegetable residue accumulation and the likely potential for future production of stable flies, the timeframes and their severity, which will impact on what management options are available to the producer/owner/manager.

WHERE DO I LOOK TO FIND STABLE FLY BREEDING?

Pages 14-28 above gave an overview of where stable fly breeding has been found, but in summary look for:

- (i) Any rotting vegetable matter from several days to several months old in some cases
- (ii) Presence of continual moisture, previous moisture (water spills etc)
- (iii) Presence of previous rotting vegetable matter/manure (since removed, but pupae remain in soil)
- (iv) Accumulations of animal manure (either alone or in combination with straw or any other OM)
- (v) Areas where reject vegetables have been fed out to livestock
- (vi) Old hay stacks/bales or silage that has been wet and/or left in the field after feeding out
- (vii) Washdown areas and drains where manures and vegetable matter can accumulate in the soil
- (viii) Heaps/stacks of animal manure, lawn clippings exposed to rain/irrigation.

SAMPLING TO CONFIRM STABLE FLY PRESENCE

In any situations where you need to take samples of material (eg rotting vegetable matter, reject vegetable produce, animal manures, soiled straw bedding, wet piles of grass clippings etc) to confirm the presence of stable flies, please follow the procedure listed below:

- 1) Take photographs of the fly larvae, fly pupae or fly eggs in situ.
- 2) Take a sub-sample of the material and place on a 5cm bed of dry sand inside a plastic box such as a 2L ice cream container.
- 3) Secure fly proof mesh over the plastic box to ensure that no other flies can contaminate the sample by laying eggs or live larvae onto the rotting material (always secure two rubber bands over the mesh lid in case one breaks). Make sure that when you place the mesh lid on the container that you do not trap any adult flies, which may be hanging around and attracted by the material in the sample.
- 4) Place 1 piece of evidence tape or a sticker (signed and dated) over each of the 4 sides of the box on to the mesh.
- 5) Label the box with Exhibit number (Initials of person collecting followed by a number, e.g. PAC 1 for first exhibit, PAC 2 for second exhibit etc).
- 6) Label the box with sample details, collection time, date, who collected, property details, resource the fly larvae/pupae were found in etc.
- 7) Photograph the sealed box showing the dates and signatures on the evidence tape / white sticker.
- 8) Complete exhibit label and attached to sample box.
- 9) Make notes documenting the seizure. Record the location using appropriate methods, e.g. Photographs (showing position relative to buildings, roads etc) written notes and GPS co-ordinates.
- 10) The sample of “infested” material needs to be kept at room temperature in a safe location and/or transported to DAFWA (3 Baron-Hay Court, South Perth) for processing.
- 11) The adult flies will emerge from the material over the next few weeks; it may take 3-4 weeks before all adult fly emergence is complete and the flies then sorted for counting and species identification.
- 12) Ensure continuity of the exhibit is recorded on exhibit label and the storage location is recorded.

IF YOU REQUIRE A RAPID FLY IDENTIFICATION

If you require a rapid fly identification, then submit a sample of > 10 fly larvae and/or pupae preserved in 70% ethanol for identification . High magnification microscopy by Dr David Cook (Entomologist) using key larval and pupal morphological features can confirm they are *Stomoxys calcitrans*. In the event of pending compliance, both sampling methods above should be used, i.e. larvae/pupae in 70% ethanol and live specimens.

- 1) Take photographs of larvae or pupae in situ.

- 2) Collect at least 10 larvae and / or pupae and place in specimen container with 70% ethanol solution.
- 3) Place the lid on the container. Place one piece of evidence tape or a sticker (signed and dated) over each the lid and two sides of the container.
- 4) Label the box with Exhibit number (Initials of person collecting followed by a number, e.g. PAC 1 for first exhibit, PAC 2 for second exhibit etc).
- 5) Photograph the sealed container showing the dates and signatures on the evidence tape / white sticker.
- 6) Label the container with Exhibit number (Initials of person collecting followed by a number, e.g. PAC 1 for first exhibit, PAC for second exhibit etc).
- 7) Complete exhibit label and attached to sample container.
- 8) Make notes documenting the seizure. Record the location using appropriate methods, e.g. Photographs (showing position to buildings, signs etc, written notes and GPS co-ordinates.
- 9) Ensure continuity of the exhibit is recorded on exhibit label and its storage location is recorded.
- 10) Deliver the sample marked "Attention: Dr David Cook, DAFWA (3 Baron-Hay Court, South Perth)

MANAGEMENT OPTIONS FOR STABLE FLY CONTROL

Please refer to the Biosecurity and Agriculture Management (Stable Fly) Management Plan 2013 for Management options relevant to any situations where stable fly breeding is found. Below is a summary of the most likely significant sources of stable fly and their best management:

SOURCES

VEGETABLE CROP RESIDUES LEFT AFTER HARVEST

(For example: broccoli, cabbage, cauliflower, lettuce, celery, leek, spring onions, silverbeet)

- Minimise the harvesting period as much as possible – multiple harvesting of the same area results in the first lot of vegetable waste left behind starting to rot and attract stable flies.
- Turn off all watering of the harvested area **AS SOON AS HARVESTING IS COMPLETE**
- High speed mulch the crop residues (leaves, stalks, reject fruit) left after harvest as soon as possible and at least within 3 days after harvest is complete
- Apply a pesticide application to the mulched crop residues and leave undisturbed and unwatered for **AT LEAST 7 DAYS**.
- Incorporate the dry crop residues into soil no sooner than 7 days after mulching and spraying.

REJECT PRODUCE

(eg eggplants, rockmelons, strawberries, zucchinis, paprikas)

- Remove and/or collect all rotting reject produce
- Place in a large, open pit
- Spray the reject produce with an approved pesticide OR cover with at least 50cm of soil daily OR
- Spray the reject produce inbetween the rows of growing crop every 3 days with an approved pesticide.
- DO NOT place reject produce and any processing scraps into piles under any circumstances
- Leaves from processed produce can be spread out thinly on the ground to dry.

VEGETABLES FED OUT TO LIVESTOCK

(eg carrots, corn, broccoli, spring onions)

- Place reject vegetables out for livestock in long, thin lines
- Do NOT place in one big pile
- Feed out vegetables in different locations around paddocks and yards on each occasion

ANIMAL MANURES , FEEDSTUFFS AND SOILED BEDDING

- Remove accumulations of manure, soiled bedding and/or spilled grain feed from animal pens, feed troughs, under fence lines and around water troughs every 3 weeks
- Place into windrows if composting, or into a large, manageable pile
- If no fly larvae are present in the material, then cover and seal completely with black plastic
- If any fly larvae are present in the material, SPRAY with an approved pesticide THEN cover and seal completely with black plastic

In addition to identifying sources where stable flies lay eggs and allow larvae to grow and develop into adult flies, it is important to acknowledge that something can still be done to minimise the impact on affected livestock, whether it be cattle, horses, dogs, goats and humans affected either at their home, place of work or in recreational areas. Below is some practical advice and/or information that you can give to livestock producers, owners, rural residents and the broader community to help minimise stable flies.

AFFECTED LIVESTOCK

CATTLE

Figure 63. Huge numbers of stable flies can affect cattle, from calves (L) to adult animals (R).

(1) Feedlot & Pen Management: Any high density feeding and holding yards for cattle quickly accumulate a lot of manure. Regular clean-outs are essential to prevent nuisance flies developing in the manure. As the manure ages, stable flies are more likely to breed in this manure. The manure should not be put into large piles and left exposed to flies. All feed bins and troughs need to be kept dry so that pelletised feed and grain does not become wet, ferment and allow for stable flies to develop. Ensure water troughs do not over-fill and wet manure and feed that accumulates underneath the troughs. Similarly, silage and hay if left exposed and wet for any extended period of time will ferment and provide stable flies with an ideal breeding place. Use ground corn cob bedding (non-absorbent) to suppress larval growth instead of straw bedding or apply cyromazine granules under straw bedding to prevent larval growth.

Cattle dung in rangeland pastures is NOT a source of stable fly breeding as stable flies are only attracted to old dung that is at least 3 weeks old. In our hot, dry climate the cattle dung pads have either been removed by dung beetles during the summer months or the dung has dried out and won't sustain any fly larvae.

(2) Feeding out Vegetables: If you feed out reject vegetables to cattle, make sure that you only feed out enough vegetables that will be mostly eaten. Any excess vegetable matter will rot when left on the ground and combined with the cattle's manure and urine, provide an ideal place for stable flies to develop. Putting the vegetables out in long, thin lines ensures it is mostly eaten and any residue left behind rapidly dries out.

(3) Insecticides and Repellents can be used on your cattle to keep stable flies away. There are numerous products on the market ranging from backline pour-on's and sprays to insecticide-impregnated ear tags. The relative effectiveness of these products in controlling stable flies has not been tested. Most repellents have been found to last anywhere from a few days to maybe a day or two at best, given the huge numbers of stable flies affecting livestock in and around Perth. Please check the website www.apvma.gov.au for up to date information on products registered for use on cattle in WA. Appendix 1 has a list of currently registered pesticides against stable flies on cattle in WA (current as at June, 2016). Drenching your cattle with a range of avermectin-based drugs that are systemic anti-parasitic drugs against internal and external parasites will kill any stable flies that bite the cattle over at least 3-4 weeks. Although it involves a sub-cutaneous injection to each animal it provides a reasonable window of protection from the stable flies.

(4) Stable Fly Traps can be used to catch and remove this fly from areas where your cattle feed and shelter. Protein-based traps will NOT catch stable flies, but a whole other lot of nuisance flies including bush flies, house flies and blowflies that still annoy cattle.

AFFECTED LIVESTOCK

HORSES

(1) Protective Equipment: Covering your horse with protective face guards, body rugs, and leg guards can reduce the numbers of stable flies able to inflict bites on your horses. As the fly mostly targets the lower limbs and underbelly, they are not able to prevent every fly from attacking your horses, so some repellent sprays and insecticidal pour-on products will help in addition. There are now horse protective rugs available that wrap underneath the belly of horses for more secure holding and will protect that area of the horse from stable fly bites. Also, there are some horse rugs with permethrin impregnated into the fabric that act as a repellent to blood-feeding flies without insecticide being in direct contact with the horses skin. You can apply a permethrin rinse yourself to horse rugs as well as spraying on a range of residual sprays (see list in Appendix 2)

Figure 64. Horse owners have resorted to putting protective rugs, fly boots (L) and face masks (R) on their horses to reduce the numbers of stable flies affecting their animals.

(2) Manure & Straw Bedding Management: Horse manure and straw bedding that is left unchanged for more than a week can start to rot and ferment and allow stable flies to lay eggs on this material. Regular removal of manure from stalls, pens and paddocks will help reduce a range of nuisance flies from breeding. Particular attention to wet and soiled straw bedding will prevent stable flies from developing.

(3) Insecticides and Repellents can be used on horses to keep stable flies away. There are numerous products including insecticidal backline pour on's, rinses, sprays or ear tags through to repellent sprays and creams. The relative effectiveness of these products in controlling stable flies has not been tested. Natures Botanical Cream (with rosemary and cedarwood oil) is particularly good at keeping stable flies off horses. Repellents do not kill the flies, but stop them landing on and biting your horse. Most repellents only last several hours, so given the huge numbers affecting horses around Perth, it is best to use 3-4 different repellents, rotating to a different one every day. Please check www.apvma.gov.au for up to date information on products registered for use on horses in WA. Appendix 2 has a list of currently registered pesticides against stable flies on horses in WA (current to June, 2016). A range of anthelmintic drugs used as internal and external parasite control can kill any stable flies that bite horses, providing at least 3-4 weeks protection.

(4) Stable Fly Traps can be used to specifically catch and remove this fly from areas where your horses feed and spend most of their time. Protein-based traps will NOT catch stable flies, but a whole other lot of nuisance flies including bush flies, house flies and blowflies that still annoy horses.

AFFECTED ANIMALS

DOGS

Figure 65. Dogs can often be targeted by stable flies, causing them great distress, especially when a wound starts to bleed, which just attracts more stable flies (R).

One of the many common names for the stable fly is the “dog fly” and for good reason as they can attack dogs as well as humans. The fly loves to bite and draw blood from the ears of dogs, where the blood vessels are very close to the skin surface.

(1) Protecting Ears: Smearing a number of oil-based creams and repellents on the dogs ears can protect them from stable fly bites. Vaseline, Nature’s Botanical Crème, dieseline and other oils can keep the flies away at least from their ears. The rosemary and cedarwood oils in Nature’s Botanical Cream make it a very effective cream against stable flies. Some repellent sprays and insecticidal sprays will help in addition. Spraying your dog’s bedding and in and around their kennel and feeding area will keep flies away from where your dog rests/sleeps. You can dip your dog’s blankets/bedding into a permethrin rinse yourself (see list in Appendix 3).

(2) Manure Management: Dog manure is an attractive manure to stable flies although they rarely develop in this material as larvae and survive through to adulthood as the manure quickly dries out. However, it is always wise to regularly clean up and bury dog manure to prevent lots of nuisance flies from hanging around your yard, dog kennel and verandahs.

(3) Insecticides and Repellents can be used on dogs to keep stable flies away. There are numerous products on the market including sprays, repellents, creams, rinses and shampoos sprays. The relative effectiveness of these products in controlling stable flies has not been tested. Repellents do not kill the flies, but are designed to stop them landing on and biting your dog. Most repellents only last from a few hours to several days at best. Please check the APVMA website www.apvma.gov.au for up to date information on products registered for dogs in WA. Some flea control products that are systemic in dogs will ensure that any flies that bite and draw blood from your dog will ultimately die. Appendix 3 has a list of currently registered pesticides against stable flies on dogs in WA (current as at June 2016).

(4) Stable Fly Traps can be used to specifically catch and remove this fly from areas where dogs spend most of their time. Protein-based traps will NOT catch stable flies, but a whole other lot of nuisance flies including bush flies, house flies and blowflies that still annoy dogs, but not nearly as much as the biting fly.

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APPENDIX 1

REGISTERED CHEMICALS AGAINST STABLE FLIES ON CATTLE IN WA

POUR-ONS	ACTIVE	WHP	ESI
ELANCO DEMIZE POUR-ON FOR CATTLE	25g/L z-cypermethrin	14	28
ELANCO ELECTOR PSP ANIMAL PREMISE SPRAY	480g/L spinosad	21	?
DELTAMAX QUICK-DOSE POUR-ON FOR CATTLE	Deltamethrin	0	21
COOPERS COOPAFLY POUR-ON FLY AND CATTLE	Deltamethrin	0	21
DELTAFLY EASY-DOSE POUR-ON CATTLE FLY TREATMENT	Deltamethrin	0	21
ARREST EASY-DOSE POUR-ON FLY TREATMENT	15g/L deltamethrin	0	21
SWISH POUR-ON CATTLE LICE AND FLY TREATMENT	15g/L deltamethrin	0	21
COOPERS EASY-DOSE POUR-ON LICE/FLY TREATMENT	15g/L deltamethrin	0	21
BOMBARD POUR-ON CATTLE LICE/FLY TREATMENT	15g/L deltamethrin	0	21
VIRBAC POUR-ON CATTLE LICE AND FLY TREATMENT	15g/L deltamethrin	0	21
FEEDLOT SITUATIONS			
NEPOREX 2 GR INSECT GROWTH REGULATOR (GRANULAR)	20g/kg Cyromazine	NA	NA
HOKOEX FLY LARVIDICE (GRANULAR)	20g/kg Cyromazine	NA	NA
ALODEX FLY LARVICIDE (GRANULAR)	20g/kg Cyromazine	NA	NA
FLY REPELLENTS			
PHARMA-CHEMICAL SUPERSHIELD INSECT REPELLENT FOR FLIES & BITING INSECTS	2g/L pyrethrins etc.	0	0
SAINT BERNARD PETCARE INSECT REPELLENT FOR FLIES & BITING INSECTS	20g/L diethyltoluamide	0	0

WHP = With Holding Period for milk and meat

ESI = Export Slaughter Interval

NA = Not Applicable

Information correct as at 13th June, 2016

APPENDIX 2

REGISTERED CHEMICALS AGAINST STABLE FLIES ON HORSES IN WA

SPRAYS/RINSES/POUR-ONS
DELTAMAX QUICK-DOSE POUR-ON CATTLE LICE AND FLY TREATMENT
BLUE RIBBON READY TO USE INSECTICIDE
PHARMA-CHEM SWAT INSECTICIDE FOR HORSES
PHARMA-CHEMICAL QUICK-KILL RINSE/SPRAY CONCENTRATE
COOPERS EASY-DOSE POUR-ON CATTLE LICE AND FLY TREATMENT
FIDO'S PERMETHRIN RINSE CONCENTRATE FOR DOGS AND HORSES
SWIFT READY-TO-USE INSECTICIDAL POUR-ON FOR HORSES
Y-TEX BRUTE INSECTICIDE FOR HORSES
DAVID KURITCH – ALLERGIC REACTIONS TO INSECT BITES
FLYAWAY INSECTICIDAL SPRAY FOR HORSES
EQUIS SHOO FLY INSECTICIDAL SPRAY AND WACH CONC FOR HORSES
SWISH POUR-ON CATTLE LICE AND FLY TREATMENT
DELTAFLY EASY-DOSE POUR-ON CATTLE LICE AND FLY TREATMENT
EQUIFLY POUR-ON FLY INSECTICIDE FOR HORSES
COOPERS EQUIFLY POUR-ON FOR HORSES
VIRBAC FLY AWAY POUR-ON FOR HORSES
BOMBARD POUR-ON CATTLE LICE AND FLY TREATMENT
SHIELD POUR-ON FOR HORSES
NUCIDOL 200EC INSECTICIDE AND ACARICIDE
ELANCO ELECTOR PSP ANIMAL PREMISE SPRAY
VETSENSE PERMETROL INSECTICIDAL SPRAY FOR DOGS AND HORSES
INCA BAN-FLY INSECTICIDAL SPRAY FOR ANIMALS
DERMCARE PERMOXIN INSECTICIDAL SPRAY & RINCE CONC. FOR DOGS & HORSES
FLY REPELLENTS/CREAMS
PHARMA-CHEMICAL SUPERSHIELD INSECT REPELLENT FOR FLIES
JOESEPH LYDDY N-DEM INSECTICIDAL LOTION
SAINT BERNARD PETCARE INSECT REPELLENT FOR FLIES
ARISTOPET ANIMAL HEALTH FLY REPELLENT SPRAY FOR HORSES & DOGS

APPENDIX 3

REGISTERED CHEMICALS AGAINST STABLE FLIES ON DOGS IN WA

PRODUCT NAME
DERMCARE PERMOXIN INSECTICIDAL SPRAY/RINSE CONCENTRATE
BLUE RIBBON READY TO USE INSECTICIDE
PHARMA-CHEMICAL QUICK-KILL RINSE/SPRAY CONCENTRATE
FIDO'S PERMETHRIN RINSE CONCENTRATE FOR DOGS AND HORSES
PHARMA-CHEMICAL SUPERSHIELD INSECT REPELLENT FOR FLIES
TROY PROTECTA BITING INSECT REPELLENT & ANTISEPTIC CREAM
TROY REPEL-X INSECTICIDAL & REPELLENT SPRAY
EQUIS SHOO FLY INSECTICIDAL SPRAY & WASH CONC FOR HORSES
ELANCO AH0495 ELECTOR PSP ANIMAL PREMISE SPRAY
VETSENSE PERMETROL INSECTICIDAL SPRAY FOR DOGS & HORSES
COOPERS EQUIFLY POUR-ON FOR HORSES
VIRBAC FLY AWAY POUR-ON FOR HORSES
SAINT BERNARD PETCARE INSECT REPELLENT FOR FLIES
ADVANTIX FOR DOGS
ARISTOPET ANIMAL HEALTH FLY REPELLENT SPRAY FOR HORSES & DOGS

APPENDIX 4

REGISTERED CHEMICALS AGAINST BITING FLIES ON CLOTHING IN WA

Dip clothing/animal bedding/horse blankets thoroughly for 10 minutes

Drain on flat, non-absorbent surface first before hanging up to dry further

PRODUCT NAME	
CHAINDRITE PERFORCE 500 RESIDUAL INSECTICIDE	<i>12mL/1L of water</i>
DRAGNET RESIDUAL INSECTICIDE	<i>12mL/1L of water</i>
PERIGEN DEFENCE RESIDUAL INSECTICIDE	<i>12mL/1L of water</i>
PERMASHIELD RESIDUAL INSECTICIDE	<i>12mL/1L of water</i>
PERMESHIELD 500 RESIDUAL INSECTICIDE	<i>12mL/1L of water</i>
PERMETHRIN 500 TIMBER & RESIDUAL INSECTICIDE	<i>12mL/1L of water</i>
ENVIROMAX PERMETHRIN 500EC	<i>12mL/1L of water</i>
PERMEX EC	<i>12mL/1L of water</i>
POUNCE 500 TIMBER & RESIDUAL INSECTICIDE	<i>12mL/1L of water</i>

APPENDIX 5

STABLE OR BITING FLY TRAPS

White boards with a sticky surface will catch stable or biting flies as they like to rest on a cool, vertical surface after a blood meal. By contrast, protein-based traps (rotting or decomposing smell) put out to catch houseflies, blowflies, bushflies and other nuisance flies WILL NOT catch any stable flies. Below are some options for you to catch stable flies with boards and/or specific traps placed either around your house (verandahs, fence posts, kennels) or livestock yards and paddocks where animals typically congregate.

White Board Traps

The simplest form of stable fly trap uses a white board or panel (see pics below) with a non-drying glue painted onto the surface to catch the flies. These traps are specific to stable flies and catch very little else. Secure the white board to a star picket or along a fence line with cable ties at 0.5m from the ground to avoid getting covered in dirt and dust. Paint one or both sides of the board with the non-drying glue such as Stikem® (available in Australia from bugsforbugs.com.au or theolivecentre.com in 3kg or 11kg tins or Tanglefoot® from entosupplies.com.au (2.26kg tin). A 3kg tin will easily paint 30 white boards. The glue must be heated on a hot plate first till it is clear and can be easily applied using a broad paint scraper. It must be applied quickly and any drops on you or anything else will only come off with baby oil. You can buy white boards such as Corflute, Melamine, Aligloss, Acrylic Sheets, High Density Polyethylene Boards, Masonite or Stainless Steel Minisheets, which come in sizes from 600mm x 600mm up to 900mm x 600mm and 1200mm x 900mm. Once the boards are covered with flies, remove the glue and flies with a paint scraper before re-application. Multiple boards cleared daily and re-painted with glue can remove several thousand stable flies.

As an alternative to applying non-drying glue yourself, there are 100m rolls of white or clear film available from ocos.co.uk that have non-drying glue on both sides; simply stick the film onto any white boards and peel off when covered with flies. The rolls of film come in either 15cm or 30cm wide strips, so you can put several strips on the white board depending upon the size of the board you choose.

Figure 1. Williams trap white board (L), and corflute boards covered with stable flies (Centre & R)

Olson Sticky Traps for Stable/Biting Flies

The Olson Traps consist of an Alsynite cylinder covered with a disposable, sticky clear film. Fasten the trap to a fence post or stake pushed into the ground. The traps (cylinder plus stake plus 2 sticky sleeves) are available at rinconvitova.com or amazon.com with packs of 10 replacement sticky films available. Remove and replace the films when covered with stable flies and/or dust. Aeroxon Barn & Stable Fly Catcher is a large roll of sticky tape (20cm x 1m) for hanging in barns, stables and kennels (available from biconet.com) and 7m flycatcher sticky rolls from vetnpetdirect.com.au.

Figure 2. Olson Biting Fly Traps are Alsynite cylinders covered with a clear sticky film

Disposable Stable Fly Traps

Small, commercial versions of the Williams Trap are available but with the advantage of being easier to handle and disposable when full of flies. The traps go under several different names, eg Farnam Bite Free Stable Fly Trap, Starbar Bite Free Stable Fly Trap and EZ Sticky Fly Trap. These traps are available from pacificbiologics.com.au or from the US at either: valleyvet.com, cattlestore.com or rinconvitova.com. Not all US suppliers may ship to Australia, so check first.

Figure 3. Disposable Stable Fly traps

Cloth Target Treated Traps

White cloth soaked in insecticide can be used as a semi-permanent killing system that attracts stable flies, which die when contacting the cloth. These have been shown to kill stable flies for up to 3 months when left in the field/paddock. Keep away from animals and watering by sprinklers. Keep the cloth pulled and secured tightly between two posts/star pickets and with the base no more than 0.5m above ground level and clear of vegetation. Soak the cloth in either 0.1% solution of lambda-cyhalothrin or other pyrethroid/permethrins and let dry on a flat surface prior to hanging up. Other insecticides to use could include bifenthrin, cyfluthrin, cyfenothrin, tetramethrin or deltamethrin.

Figure 4. Cloth Target Treated Traps are a semi-permanent option for killing stable flies in the field.

Protein-based traps that catch houseflies, blowflies and bushflies DON'T catch stable flies.

Figure 5. Examples of protein-based traps available in Australia for catching nuisance flies

APPENDIX 6

TYPICAL SITUATIONS WHERE STABLE FLIES BREED

Vegetable crop residues

Reject produce

Old, wet hay bales

Old animal manure build-up

Spilled and wet animal feed

Soiled animal bedding

Piles of wet lawn clippings

Poultry manure stacks (wet)

Vegetables fed to livestock

Olive pressing residue

Wet horse manure & straw

Poorly managed compost

Typical situations where stable flies lay eggs and develop into adult flies.

Disclaimer: This brochure simply provides information on products available to catch and/or kill stable flies. Any product omission is unintentional and information is current as at August, 2015. Please contact Dr David Cook for more specific advice to suit your situation and circumstances for stable fly control in either rural, rural-residential or urban environments.

Author: Dr David Cook, Department of Agriculture & Food WA. August, 2016

Stable Fly Development from Plant Derived Substrates**Reference**

Bay grass	Freshwater bay grasses	Simmons & Dove 1941
Beetroot	Rotting piles of leaves	Cook et al. 2011, 2017
Broccoli	Rotting crop residues (leaves/stalks/fruit)	Cook et al. 2011, 2017
Broccolini	Rotting crop residues left after harvest	Cook et al. 2017
Cabbage	Rotting crop residues	Cook et al. 2011, 2017
Carrots	Rotting carrots in residue pits	Cook et al. 2011, 2017
Cauliflower	Rotting crop residues	Cook et al. 2011, 2017
Celery	Rotting crop residues	Cook et al. 2011, 2017
Chinese radish (daikon)	Rotting piles of whole radishes and/or leaves	Simmons & Dove 1942
Citrus leaves	rotting piles of citrus leaves	Cook et al. 2011, 2017
Coffee plants	Coffee plant pulp residue	Solarzano pers comm.
Coriander	Rotting coriander root	Solarzano pers comm
Corn	Trashed corn crop residues rotting in soil	Cook et al. 2017
Eggplants	Rotting reject eggplant fruit	Cook et al. 2011, 2017
Grass	Wet piles of grass clippings	Cook et al. 2017
Hay stacks/bales	Rotting hay stacks and bales	Bishopp 1913
		Broce et al. 2005
		Hall et al. 1982
		Cancardo et al. 2013
		Talley et al. 2009
		Cook et al. 2017
		Cook pers comm.
Honey Dew Melons	Rotting reject melons	Cook et al. 2017
Leek	Rotting reject leeks	Cook et al. 2011, 2017
Lettuce	Rotting lettuces, root stumps	Cook et al. 2017
Olive Pomace	Olive Pressing Residues	Cook et al. 2017
Onions	Reject onions in pit	Cook et al. 2017
Organic Material	Rotting organic material	King & Lenert 1936
		Meyer & Petersen 1983
Paprika (bell peppers)	Rotting reject paprika fruit	Cook et al. 2011, 2017
Parsnip	Rotting piles of parsnip leaves and reject fruit	Cook et al. 2017
Peanut vine litter	Rotting peanut vine litter	Simmons & Dove 1941
Pineapple	Rotting pineapple crop residues	Solorzano et al. 2015
Pumpkins	Rotting reject grey, jap & butternut pumpkins	Cook et al. 2011, 2017
Rockmelon	Rotting reject fruit	Cook et al. 2011, 2017
Silage (green chop)	Green chop	Williams et al. 1980
Silage	Open silage pit	Cook et al. 2017
Silage		Cancado et al. 2013
Silverbeet	Rotting silverbeet leaves and root stumps	Cook et al. 2011, 2017
Snow Peas	Piles of reject snow peas	Cook et al. 2011, 2017
Spring Onion	Piles of reject spring onion	Cook et al. 2017
Squash	Rotting reject squash	Cook et al. 2017
Strawberries	Rotting piles of reject strawberries	Cook et al. 2017
Sugar cane bagasse		Cancado et al. 2013
Sugar cane vignasse		Oda & Arantes 2009
		Cancado et al. 2013
Sugar can filter cake		Cancado et al. 2013
Sugar cane plant residues		Oda & Arantes 2009
		Cancado et al. 2013
Turnip	Rotting reject turnips	Cook et al. 2011, 2017
Zucchini	Rotting reject zucchinis	Cook et al. 2011, 2017
Weeds	Rotting wild radish weeds	Cook et al. 2017

Weeds		Simmons & Dove 1941
Wild melons	rotting reject pig melons	Cook et al. 2017

Stable Fly develop in low numbers from these substrates:

Capsicums	<1 stable fly/rotting fruit	Cook et al. 2011, 2017
Chilli Peppers	<1 stable fly/rotting fruit.	Cook et al. 2017
Grass	<1 stable fly/grass cake from power mowers	Ware 1966
Potatoes	<3 stable fly/rotting potato	Cook et al. 2011, 2017
Seaweed	rotting seaweed in river mouth near ocean	Cook et al. 2017
Tomato	<1 stable fly/rotting fruit	Cook et al. 2011, 2017
Watermelon	<2 stable fly/rotting melon	Cook et al. 2011, 2017

Stable Fly Unable to Develop from these Substrates:

Cherry Tomatoes	no stable flies developed from these	Cook pers comm.
Cucumbers	rotting cucumber fruit	Cook et al. 2017
Grape Mark	residue left from pressing grapes skins and pips	Cook et al. 2017
Wide-bladed turtle grass (<i>Thalassia testudium</i>)		King & Lenert 1936
Narrow-bladed manatee grass (<i>Halodule wrightii</i>)		King & Lenert 1936

Pineapple associated cost of management postharvest plant residues
May 2018

Management residues plan for non-desiccated plants: Total cost \$/ha=3573

Day or week	Activity	Cost/Ha (US\$)	Comments
0	Insecticide GRI application	184.35	
3	Drainage cover	317	
4	First shredder	1006	fresh plant cut and crushing at low seed 1 ha/day / tractor
Week 1, 2, 3, 4, 5	Massive trapping.	156	Placement of white bags glue traps throughout the process of preparation 15 traps/ ha. Considering one change/week. Most time are 3 changes/ week.
Week 2, 3, 4, 5	Stable Fly sampling (immatures)	20	Sampling every 5 days
Day 10	Insecticide GRI application	184.35	Immediately after crushing.
Día 12	Second shredder	500	Hand picking of left over pineapple plant steams and crushing with shredder machine
Day 10 to 30	Disc harrows 6 times	1330	As much as possible if weather is ok to incorporate residues underground.